

ALL-ISLAND CANCER RESEARCH LANDSCAPE REPORT

*An Analysis of Cancer Research in
Ireland and Northern Ireland*

2019-2024

Irish
Cancer
Society

Information Note

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This report is the result of an All-Island Cancer Research Institute (AICRI) initiative, supported by the Irish Cancer Society as part of a strategic investment to map and strengthen cancer research across the island of Ireland.

It is based on a detailed analysis of cancer research publications from 2019–2024 across Ireland and Northern Ireland, contextualised through ecosystem insights and examples of impactful research stories on the island. Strategic recommendations are informed by data-driven, in-depth analytical methods.

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Introductory Note

***Cancer Knows No Borders,
Neither Should We***

The All-Island Cancer Research Institute

The All-Island Cancer Research Institute (AICRI) is a virtual institute that brings together researchers, clinicians, patients, and other stakeholders involved in cancer research across Ireland and Northern Ireland. Its mission is to strengthen collaboration across borders, disciplines, and sectors in order to accelerate discoveries, improve patient outcomes, and establish the island of Ireland as a global leader in cancer research and innovation. Its ethos is: “Cancer Knows No Borders, Neither Should We.”

AICRI is built on the collaboration of eleven core partner academic institutions, together with a wide network of stakeholders from across the cancer research ecosystem on the island of Ireland. These institutions and stakeholders provide a strong foundation for collaborative research, education and training, and patient-focused innovation

The Irish Cancer Society

The Irish Cancer Society, Ireland’s national cancer charity, plays a central role in driving cancer research, providing free services and supports, advocacy, and patient partnership. The Society invests significantly in cancer research each year, supporting translational, clinical trials, and survivorship research that aim to improve outcomes, care and quality of life for patients and their families. In 2024, The Society invested about €4 million in new cancer research, reflecting steady growth in its commitment to advancing world class cancer research and innovation (Irish Cancer Society, 2025a).

This commitment reflects the Society’s wider role in shaping the cancer research landscape across Ireland, fostering partnerships, and strengthening capacity. In 2023, the Irish Cancer Society both funded and partnered with AICRI to advance a cancer research landscape analysis project covering the island of Ireland (Irish Cancer Society, 2025b), which is reflected in the current report. The report creates a strong evidence base to support data-driven decisions, giving the cancer research community key insights to foster innovation and strengthen collaboration. Through this partnership, the Irish Cancer Society underlines its commitment to evidence-based, collaborative research that places patients and communities at its centre.

Foreword

Prof. William Gallagher

*Professor of Cancer Biology,
University College Dublin.*

*Co-Lead
All-Island Cancer Research
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Prof. Mark Lawler

*Professor of Digital Health,
Queen's University Belfast*

*Co-Lead
All-Island Cancer Research
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Cancer knows no borders. Every family on the island of Ireland is affected in some way by this complex set of diseases. We know, however, that cancer research can make a difference. Those treated in research active hospitals have better outcomes.

Over the last 5 years, we have brought together a coalition of the willing across Ireland and Northern Ireland to look at ways to better integrate research across our various institutions and bodies. The All-Island Cancer Research Institute (AICRI) has made great initial steps in fostering greater cross-border and inter-institutional collaboration, particularly aided by support under the North South Research Programme (NSRP), InterTrade Ireland (ITI) and the Irish Cancer Society (The Society).

In 2024, the Irish Cancer Society partnered with AICRI to develop a comprehensive knowledge base relating to the cancer research and innovation ecosystem on the island of Ireland. This landscape report is an initial key output from this collaboration and focuses on gleaning key insights from a detailed analysis of cancer research publications from Ireland and Northern Ireland over a six year period (2019-2024). This report complements the All-Island Oncology Industry Landscape Report which was launched in April 2024.

Together, these documents form a cohesive foundation for ongoing monitoring, analysis, and evidence-based strategy development.

They enable stakeholders, ranging from academic researchers and clinicians to policymakers, patient advocates, and industry partners, to better understand the current state and future opportunities within the cancer research and innovation ecosystem on the island of Ireland.

This report is particularly timely, given the announcement of a Cancer Research Strategic Framework for Northern Ireland and the pending development of a National Cancer Research Plan in Ireland, which is expected to feed into the next National Cancer Strategy in Ireland.

We are very thankful for the significant support from the Irish Cancer Society in facilitating the creation and delivery of this report.

Foreword

Edel Shovlin

*Acting Chief Executive Officer
Irish Cancer Society*

The Irish Cancer Society is the national cancer charity in the Republic of Ireland. We are a community of patients, survivors, volunteers, supporters, health and social care professionals and researchers. Together, we are working to improve the lives of people affected by cancer through our advocacy, free support and services, and research.

The Irish Cancer Society is proud to be the largest voluntary funder of cancer research in Ireland. Through our investment in world class cancer research, we aim to transform the experiences and outcomes of everyone affected by cancer across the island of Ireland.

In line with this commitment, the Irish Cancer Society are very proud partners of the All-Island Cancer Research Institute (AICRI), aiming to bring together the combined strength of cancer researchers, institutions and communities both north and south of the border, to further establish Ireland as a global leader in cancer research. As part of this partnership, the Irish Cancer Society invested in a dedicated AICRI Research Analyst to comprehensively develop this report assessing the landscape of cancer research activity in Ireland and Northern Ireland, from 2019 to 2024.

This report demonstrates the high quality, strength and impact of cancer research carried out across Ireland and Northern Ireland, and crucially, highlights that this impact is strengthened further through cross-border collaboration. For the first time, this report comprehensively assesses the cancer research ecosystem and identifies the strengths and opportunities for Ireland and Northern Ireland to develop as a world-leader of cancer research.

Importantly, as highlighted in this report, both Ireland and Northern Ireland are home to a dedicated network of cancer research leaders working hard to provide hope to people affected by cancer across the island.

The Irish Cancer Society remains committed to a future in which fewer people receive a cancer diagnosis and that everyone who needs it receives world-class care informed through excellent research. We believe that through strengthened collaboration on the island of Ireland, as well as shared infrastructure, open data and common ambition, we can move that vision closer to reality.

Preface

About This Report

This report presents the first integrated, all-island landscape analysis of cancer research across Ireland and Northern Ireland for the period 2019–2024. It brings together data on research output, quality and impact, clinical trials, research domains, cancer anatomical sites, international and industry collaborations, policy influence, patents, and workforce and gender patterns, to provide a comprehensive picture of the cancer research ecosystem on the island.

Using bibliometric and registry-linked indicators, and drawing on frameworks such as The Lancet Oncology European Groundshot Commission, the report describes overall areas of research intensity, indicates how current activity aligns with European and global priorities and highlights areas where critical gaps remain. It is intended as a practical resource for policymakers, funders, researchers, clinicians, patient advocates and industry partners to help them to shape a more coordinated, equitable and high-impact all-island response to cancer.

Acknowledgements

This report was developed through a partnership between the Irish Cancer Society and the All-Island Cancer Research Institute (AICRI). We gratefully acknowledge the guidance, support and feedback provided by colleagues in both organisations throughout the project.

We thank members of the AICRI Steering Committee (see www.aicri.org/team), the National Cancer Research Group, and the Irish Association for Cancer Research (IACR) who contributed insights, comments and suggestions during the development of the analysis and recommendations. We particularly appreciate **Chantal Halley**, Project Manager, AICRI for co-ordinating certain stakeholder engagements, as well as **Dr Claire Kilty** and **Dr Croí Buckley** (Irish Cancer Society) for their guidance, strategic input and detailed feedback on successive drafts.

We would also like to thank **Liam Cleere** (UCD Research) for training and support on research analytics. Additional support is acknowledged from the UCD-QUB All-Island Cancer Alliances project. We further acknowledge all those who contributed **Research Case Studies**, which bring the data to life by illustrating real-world impact on patients, services and innovation.

Glossary

- **AICRI** – All-Island Cancer Research Institute
- **AICRIstart** – All-island doctoral and post-doctoral training programme in precision cancer medicine
- **AllCaN** – All-Ireland Cancer Network Oesophageal Programme
- **ASJC** – All Science Journal Classification
- **CLuB** – All-Ireland Cancer Liquid Biopsies Consortium
- **COVID-19** – Coronavirus Disease 2019
- **CSO** – Central Statistics Office (Ireland)
- **CTI** – Cancer Trials Ireland
- **DCU** – Dublin City University
- **ECHoS** – Establishing Cancer Mission Hubs
- **EU** – European Union
- **EU Cancer Mission** – EU Mission on Cancer under Horizon Europe
- **Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan** – EU flagship cancer policy framework
- **EUR31** – 28 EU Member States plus Iceland, Norway and Switzerland
- **EUR32** – EUR31 countries plus the United Kingdom
- **FWCI** – Field-Weighted Citation Impact
- **HEA** – Higher Education Authority (Ireland)
- **HRB** – Health Research Board (Ireland)
- **IACR** – Irish Association for Cancer Research
- **The Society** – Irish Cancer Society
- **ICTRP** – International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO)
- **REACH Health** – Institute for Research Excellence in Advanced Clinical Healthcare (Queen’s University Belfast)
- **IRC** – Irish Research Council (now part of Research Ireland)
- **ITI** – InterTradeIreland
- **MSKCC** – Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center
- **NCCP** – National Cancer Control Programme (Ireland)
- **NCI** – National Cancer Institute (United States)
- **NCRI** – National Cancer Registry Ireland
- **NICR** – Northern Ireland Cancer Registry
- **NICTN** – Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network
- **NISRA** – Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency
- **NSRP** – North South Research Programme
- **POI** – Precision Oncology Ireland
- **PROACT** – All-island prostate cancer quality-of-life initiative
- **PROs** – Patient-Reported Outcomes
- **PPIE** – Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement
- **RCSI** – Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, University of Medicine and Health Sciences
- **RWE** – Real-World Evidence
- **SciVal** – Elsevier analytics platform based on Scopus
- **Scopus** – Elsevier bibliographic database
- **SFI** – Science Foundation Ireland (Now Research Ireland)
- **TCD** – Trinity College Dublin
- **TLO** – The Lancet Oncology
- **TU Dublin** – Technological University Dublin
- **UCD** – University College Dublin
- **UCC** – University College Cork
- **UL** – University of Limerick
- **WHO** – World Health Organization
- **WHO ICTRP** – WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform
- **WoS** – Web of Science
- **70:35 Vision** – European Cancer Organisation target of 70% long-term survival by 2035

**This glossary is intended to be as comprehensive as possible; all abbreviations are defined at their first occurrence in the report.*

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Cancer research on the island of Ireland is expanding in scale, influence, and confidence. This all-island cancer research report (2019–2024) provides a single, up-to-date, data-driven view of cancer research activity across Ireland and Northern Ireland, indicating areas of research intensity to help delineate where focused research efforts will help deliver better outcomes for patients.

It examines where research effort is concentrated, alongside patterns of activity, collaboration, and translation, to give decision-makers clear insight to align investment, strengthen collaboration, and accelerate the translation of research into more equitable cancer outcomes across the island.

Our aim is a decision-ready insight to align investment, deepen collaboration, and speed translation to equitable outcomes for patients affected by cancer.

Building on Ireland and Northern Ireland's complementary strengths, we position the island as having the potential to be a collective centre of excellence in cancer research, delivering innovation, attracting talent, and making a bigger impact. This report provides a single, up-to-date evidence base relating to cancer research outputs from the island of Ireland, with a primary focus on publications.

The **seven recommendations** that result from the analysis are practical, aligned with national and European Union cancer research strategies, and designed to ensure that excellence in discovery translates rapidly and equitably to people and places across the island over the next decade.

10,176

Between 2019 and 2024, researchers in Ireland and Northern Ireland contributed to 10,176 unique cancer publications.

Over this period, Ireland increased its publication output by nearly 50%, while Northern Ireland maintained a consistently high level of output relative to its population. Citation impact, a measure of the influence of an academic publication, was approximately twice the world average in both jurisdictions, and papers authored jointly across the border performed strongest of all. The cancer research portfolio on the island of Ireland was found to involve substantial research intensity in discovery and public health/population science, with steady progress in clinical and patient-centred research.

Cancer trials publications were highly visible internationally. Policy and patent activities indicated that research from the island informs decisions and innovation beyond academia. Around 10% of Ireland's and 12% of Northern Ireland's cancer publications were cited in policy documents. Citation within patents was also strong, with approximately 5% of cancer research papers from each jurisdiction cited in patents, and around 9% of clinical trials-linked outputs, underlining an active pipeline from evidence to innovation.

The evidence generated in this report aligns with European priorities for a balanced, impact-driven cancer research ecosystem, and with the European Cancer Organisation's 70:35 Vision (European Cancer Organisation, 2023):

Seventy percent long-term survival by 2035

Our publication analysis reveals clear gaps and potential opportunities. Cancer research activity is concentrated in discovery-led and population-health domains, particularly *genetics, prognosis, epidemiology and diagnosis*. In contrast, *screening, radiotherapy, surgery, paediatrics, palliative care and quality-of-life* tend to be under-represented within the overall portfolio. Compared with European and global benchmarks, the island of Ireland exhibits strong intensity in *diagnosis, epidemiology, clinical trials, screening and quality-of-life* research, but weaker intensity in research areas such as *surgery, systemic therapy, pathology, radiotherapy, paediatric oncology, targeted therapy and palliative care*.

At cancer anatomical site level, research across the island is most intense in *breast, colorectal, lung, haematological, skin or melanoma and oesophageal cancers*, in some cases exceeding European and global activity. *Pancreatic, uterine, liver, stomach, kidney, cervical and bladder* are comparatively under-represented relative to disease burden and international patterns, suggesting a need for greater strategic focus, although research capacity must also be considered in this regard.

Academic–industry collaboration is limited in volume but achieves very high citation impact. Authorship patterns reveal a gender gap in senior roles despite strong early-career parity. Cross-border cancer research remains a small proportion of total output yet is highly cited, highlighting significant potential to strengthen an integrated all-island cancer research and innovation ecosystem going forward.

Key Findings

1. Scale and Momentum

Between 2019 and 2024, researchers in Ireland and Northern Ireland produced 10,176 **unique cancer research publications**, after accounting for 338 papers jointly authored cross border. Ireland produced 7,646 cancer research publications over this period, increasing annual output by about 50%, while Northern Ireland produced 2,868, with 6.5% growth. On a population-adjusted basis, this corresponds to approximately 24 and 25 cancer research publications per 100,000 people per year in Ireland and Northern Ireland respectively, and more than 23 per 100,000 people per year across the island, signalling a substantial and growing cancer research effort in an overall population of 7.3 million across our shared island.

2. Quality and Influence

Citation impact, a measure of a publication's influence was consistently high, with Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) of 2.1 for Ireland and 1.9 for Northern Ireland; jointly authored Ireland–Northern Ireland papers were even better, reaching 2.3 (with FWCI of 1.0 being the world average). International and cross-border research collaborations, though small in relative numbers, produced the greatest citation impact. Across 2019–2024, there were 338 Ireland–Northern Ireland co-authored papers, continuing the post-Good Friday Agreement trajectory in which joint Ireland–Northern Ireland outputs rose more than thirteen-fold between 1998 and 2021, catalysed at least in part by the 1999 Ireland–Northern Ireland–National Cancer Institute Cancer Consortium.

3. COVID-19 Resilience

The cancer research ecosystem on the island of Ireland responded to the pandemic by shifting part of its focus towards COVID-19–related cancer challenges, without derailing the long-term upward trajectory in cancer research outputs. Across 2020–2024, researchers produced 357 COVID-related cancer papers, peaking in 2021/2022 at 4.7% of Ireland's and 7.1% of Northern Ireland's annual cancer research publication outputs. Over this period, annual cancer research publication volumes at an all-island level, and in Ireland individually, stayed above 2019 (pre-pandemic) levels; in Northern Ireland, they dipped slightly in 2020 but exceeded 2019 levels thereafter, confirming that the overall growth in cancer research activity was maintained.

4. International Standing

Within the *Oncology* domain, Ireland (FWCI of 1.9) and Northern Ireland (FWCI of 1.8) sat well above European Union and world baselines in terms of citation impact, with each publishing approximately six papers per 100,000 people per year; a similar pattern was seen in the broader *Cancer Research* domain.

5. Research Domain Intensity

We categorised cancer research publications from the island of Ireland into 14 research domains (see Section 2.3) and grouped them into four pillars: *Discovery Science* (Bench), *Clinical Intervention & Care* (Bedside), *Public Health & Population Science* (Community), and *Living With & Beyond Cancer*. Discovery Science accounted for just over 40% of all-island cancer research intensity, with Public Health & Population Science and Clinical Intervention & Care contributing approximately 29% and 24% respectively, with Living With & Beyond Cancer at around 5%. Compared with European and global patterns, the island of Ireland shows **relatively high intensity in epidemiology, diagnosis, clinical trials, screening and quality-of-life research**, but lower activity in **surgery, systemic therapy, pathology, radiotherapy, paediatrics, targeted therapy and palliative care**. The opportunity to maintain a strong discovery and population-health base while **gradually rebalancing effort** towards these treatment-focused and patient-centred domains must be considered.

6. Cancer Anatomical Sites

Publication outputs were grouped into three tiers, based on research intensity. At an all-island level, **Tier 1 sites**: *breast, colorectal, lung, haematological and skin or melanoma* anchor the research portfolio and account for just over half of all site-specific publications, broadly reflecting high-incidence cancers. **Tier 2 sites**: *prostate, oesophageal, central nervous system, head and neck/oral and ovarian* form a substantial middle band of sustained research activity. **Tier 3 sites**: liver, kidney, cervical, stomach, pancreatic, uterine and bladder, each account for under 5% of publications and include several poorer-prognosis cancers. Compared with European and global patterns, the island shows relatively stronger emphasis on breast, lung, colorectal, skin or melanoma and oesophageal cancers, while stomach and liver cancers occupy a smaller share of the portfolio. Overall, pancreatic, uterine, liver, stomach, kidney, cervical and bladder cancers emerge as potential priority areas for strategic reassessment of research focus, but need to be considered in the context of other issues, including research capacity (or the lack thereof), in those cancers.

7. Clinical Trials

Studies linked to Cancer Trials Ireland and the Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network represented a relatively small share of overall cancer research publications (127 and 63 publications, respectively, over 2019-2024), but produced internationally visible outputs with very high citation impact. Strong international collaboration was also observed in these clinical trials-linked outputs, with very significant industry-academic collaboration and measurable policy and patent reach. Between 2019 and 2024, over 80% of Cancer Trials Ireland and just over 50% of Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network-linked publications involved international collaborators, with approximately 30% and just over 10% respectively involving academic–industry partnerships, giving citation impact around seven to nine times the world average.

8. Policy and Innovation Signals

Around **10%** of cancer publications from Ireland and **12%** from Northern Ireland were cited in international policy documents, indicating that research from both jurisdictions is regularly used to inform policy, with particularly strong policy reach in Northern Ireland. Approximately **5%** of cancer publications in each jurisdiction were cited in patents, signalling translation into innovation. Clinical trials–related outputs showed even greater external reach: about 30% of Cancer Trials Ireland publications and 17% of Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network publications were cited in policy documents, and around 9% and 8% respectively were cited in patents, underlining the clear role of cancer trials as a key conduit from research to both policy and innovation.

9. Academic–Industry Collaboration

Although only about 7% of outputs involved industry partners across the island of Ireland, these collaborations **attracted exceptional influence** (FWCI of 7.0 in Ireland and 2.5 in Northern Ireland), indicating high returns from targeted public–private collaboration initiatives.

10. People, Institutions, and Leadership

Cancer research across the island is delivered by a broad, multidisciplinary workforce. Overall authorship patterns showed a similar structural constraint. Despite comparable numbers of first- and last-author papers, the senior investigator pool was smaller, with only about **6 last authors for every 10 first authors**. This limits the enhancement of leadership capacity and mentorship of early career investigators to more senior roles. Per-capita research activity was high for a system of this size, with Ireland producing roughly 9 first authors and 6 last authors per 100,000 people annually, and Northern Ireland around 8 and 4 respectively. These figures indicate an active research base; formal international benchmarking would further contextualise research performance.

The gender pipeline appears strong at entry into the cancer research workforce: women made up just over half of all first authors (a proxy of early career researchers) in both jurisdictions. However, only about one-third of last authors (a proxy of Principal Investigators/group leaders) were women, indicating a clear progression gap into senior roles.

Authorship and institutional patterns point to a highly concentrated but well-connected cancer research ecosystem, where a small number of universities drive most output while cross-border and international collaborations create a strong platform for more inclusive all-island growth

11. Strategic Alignment

The findings in this report align with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and The Lancet Oncology European Groundshot roadmap, and complement priorities in the National Cancer Strategy for Ireland 2017 to 2026 and the Cancer Strategy for Northern Ireland, 2022 to 2032. They also support the case for an All-Island Oncology Innovation Cluster, as also outlined in last year's AICRI-commissioned all-island industry ecosystem analysis.

Taken together, the findings of this report indicate that the island of Ireland is already making a significant impact in cancer research and innovation and poised to do more. **Deepening Ireland–Northern Ireland collaboration can help deliver an island-wide Centre of Excellence in cancer research and innovation, thereby maximising our potential to enhance patient outcomes and deliver societal benefits.**

Key Findings

Overall Output

IRELAND

7,646 Publications

142.1 per 100k/ 6 years
(23.7 per 100k/year)

NORTHERN IRELAND

2,868 Publications

149.3 per 100k/ 6 years
(24.9 per 100k/year)

💡 Per Capita Insight: Northern Ireland, though smaller in scale, has a slightly higher per-capita cancer research output than Ireland (24.9 vs 23.7 publications per 100,000 people annually)

Trends Over Time

+49.8%

Strong growth in publications
(2019 → 2024)

6.5%

Modest increase over six years

Cross-Border Collaboration

338 co-authored publications

Equivalent to 4.4% of Ireland's cancer outputs and 11.8% of Northern Ireland's

10,176

unique cancer publications over 6 years on the island, ~23 per 100k people annually

COVID-19 & Cancer Research on the Island

357 COVID-related cancer publications (2020–2024)

~4.1% of all cancer research outputs on the island;
~1.33 per 100k people per year

COVID-19 cancer research peaked in 2021, highlighting pandemic impacts on cancer care and outcomes

Key Findings

Cancer Research Intensity on the Island

Research Domains Clusters

Cancer Sites Tier Grouping

Cancer sites are grouped into three tiers by research intensity

Patents and Innovation Activities

Collaboration Patterns

Recommendations at a Glance

1. Create an All-Island Cancer Research Co-Centre

Establish a formal **All-Island Cancer Research Co-Centre**, linking universities, cancer centres, registries, biobanks, cancer clinical trials networks, patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) networks, patient organisations and industry partners, to help reduce fragmentation and provide patients and funders with a coherent, comprehensive ecosystem for research and innovation.

2. Consider Rebalancing the Cancer Research Portfolio

While maintaining strengths in discovery and population-health research, consider strengthening certain under-represented treatment and care domains such as *systemic therapy, surgery, radiotherapy, pathology, paediatrics, targeted therapy, palliative care and quality-of-life*. Consider giving greater strategic focus to poorer-prognosis, under-served cancer sites, including *pancreatic, uterine, liver, stomach, kidney, cervical and bladder* cancers, provided there already exists sufficient research capacity, so that the cancer research effort more closely reflects disease burden and service needs across the island.

3. Elevate Cross-Border Cancer Research to at Least 10% of Outputs by 2030

Use joint calls, shared academic/clinical posts, integrated training pathways and shared registries, biobanks and trial networks to increase Ireland–Northern Ireland co-authored cancer research to at least 10% of all-island outputs by 2030.

4. Expand Clinical Trials and Real World Evidence Studies to Enhance Equitable Access to Innovation

Expand cancer clinical trials and real-world evidence studies, especially in underserved and non-pharmacological areas, and embed patient-reported outcomes and quality-of-life measures, so that a currently small but highly influential trials portfolio can grow and drive fair access to innovation and socio-economic benefit across the island.

5. Create an All-Island Cancer Intelligence and Policy Hub

Aligning with the recent eHealth Hub for Cancer report (“Harnessing the Power of Data to Transform Cancer Research, Care and Innovation Across the Island of Ireland”), establish a dedicated **All-Island Cancer Intelligence and Policy Hub** that draws on existing and emerging cancer data resources and works with data custodians across the island to generate actionable insight for policy, health technology assessment (HTA), implementation and service planning.

6. Scale Academia–Industry Collaboration Through Clustering

Given the impact of joint academic-industry publications, establish an **All-Island Oncology Innovation Cluster** to coordinate academia–industry partnerships, build critical mass and unlock the high-impact, high-return potential of industry-linked cancer research.

7. Build a Sustainable and Diverse Cancer Research Workforce

Introduce all-island career frameworks with protected research time, cross-border fellowships, leadership programmes and explicit gender-equity targets to broaden the leadership base and convert a strong entry pipeline into a diverse, sustainable senior research leadership cohort.

SECTION 1

SETTING THE SCENE

1.1 Why a Landscape Analysis Now? The Report's Scope and Objectives

Cancer represents one of the most significant health challenges across the island of Ireland, with approximately one in two individuals expected to develop the disease during their lifetime.

According to the National Cancer Registry Ireland (2024) and Northern Ireland Cancer Registry (2025), there were

An annual average of 41,654 new cancer and related tumour cases diagnosed during 2020–2022 in Ireland and annual average of 14,171 new cancer cases in Northern Ireland.

An estimated annual 9,797 deaths in Ireland (2020-2022) and 4,561 deaths in Northern Ireland (2018-2022).

An estimated 220,728 and 107,619 people living with cancer in Ireland and Northern Ireland at the end of 2022.

These numbers mirror wider European and global trends. Cancer is responsible for almost one-quarter of all deaths across the European Union (EU) (EuroStat, 2021), and there were nearly 20 million new cases worldwide in 2022 (World Cancer Research Fund, 2025). In this context, the burden of cancer in Ireland and Northern Ireland underlines the need for a co-ordinated, evidence-driven cancer research ecosystem across the island, which this All-Island Cancer Research Landscape report begins to map from the perspective of published output.

Policy approaches across Ireland, Northern Ireland, and Europe affirm the central role of cancer research in cancer control. However, they differ in how clearly they set out pathways for delivery of this research. The National Cancer Strategy for Ireland 2017–2026 recognises the importance of research across prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and survivorship. It also included the establishment of a National Cancer Research Group to align research with cancer control priorities. In Northern Ireland, the Cancer Strategy 2022–2032 presents a detailed vision shaped by co-production with patients and professionals (Department of Health, 2022).

It commits to embedding research in services, widening access to clinical trials, and investing in data and diagnostic innovation. A dedicated Cancer Research Strategic Framework for Northern Ireland has recently been published. In Ireland, dedicated cancer research plans are at an early stage; a National Cancer Research Plan has recently been commissioned. Northern Ireland is at a more advanced stage; the new framework provides an initial strategic direction for cancer research. Together, these activities highlight a shared recognition of cancer research as an essential component of cancer care. They also underline the need for stronger alignment of research priorities with resources and investment, an area where evidence such as this landscape analysis can make a timely contribution.

At a European level, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan (European Commission, 2021) and the EU Cancer Mission set a coordinated agenda for tackling cancer across the EU (European Commission, 2024). The Cancer Mission brings research, innovation and public health into a single mission-oriented framework. Europe's Beating Cancer Plan calls for investment in screening, genomics, biomarker-driven precision oncology, digital health and strengthened infrastructures such as Comprehensive Cancer Centres and the European Health Data Space. Together, these initiatives place research at the core of prevention, early detection, innovative treatment, and quality-of-life improvements. The Lancet Oncology (TLO) European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al, 2023a), the most comprehensive analysis of

cancer research activity in Europe to date, further codified these priorities by analysing 12 years of cancer research data across Europe. It highlighted strengths in discovery science and innovation, but also exposed critical gaps, particularly in prevention, radiotherapy, surgery, survivorship, health systems and implementation research. The TLO report (Lawler et al, 2023a) sets out a patient-centred, evidence-driven roadmap for cancer research in Europe. It highlighted the need to address inequalities across Europe and proposed its 70:35 vision:

Achieving 70% average survival for all European cancer patients by 2035

Building on the momentum generated by these initiatives, the ECHoS project was launched in 2023 to establish National Cancer Mission Hubs across all EU member states and associated countries (European Commission, 2025). These Hubs act as catalysts for collaboration and coordination. In Ireland, the National Cancer Control Programme (NCCP) and AICRI are jointly leading the Irish element of this ECHoS EU Cancer Mission project, working to develop a National Cancer Mission Hub to better connect research with policy and practice.

This current analysis also builds on prior work on this island that evidences the value of cross-border collaboration and health diplomacy. Examples include evaluations of the outputs of the Ireland–Northern Ireland–United States National Cancer Institute (NCI) tripartite agreement and the cancer legacy of the Good Friday Agreement (Lewison et al, 2020; Lawler et al, 2023b). Together, these studies articulate the need for coordinated, data-driven investment to reduce fragmentation and accelerate cancer research impact across the island.

There is also a growing evidence base that research-active hospitals deliver better patient outcomes. In England, hospital Trusts with sustained high participation in interventional cancer trials had lower postoperative mortality and improved survival for all colorectal cancer patients, not only trial participants (Downing et al, 2017). Broader studies similarly link research activity with improved healthcare performance and outcomes (Boaz et al., 2015; Gibson et al., 2024). The TLO European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al, 2023a) also highlighted the link between research and better outcomes, indicating that cancer patients treated in research-active hospitals have better outcomes than those who are not.

Why 2019–2024?

This six-year window provides a contemporary deep-dive into the cancer research publication outputs on the island of Ireland. It updates and extends previous European and all-island analyses (Lawler et al, 2023a; Lewison et al, 2020). By focusing on the most recent period, including the years in which COVID-19 significantly disrupted research systems, it offers a robust baseline for tracking future progress. It also provides a forward-looking lens on emerging strengths, gaps and opportunities. The timeframe aligns with the development and implementation of new cancer research strategies in Ireland and Northern Ireland, maximising the relevance of this landscape analysis for research policy, strategic planning and investment.

Against this backdrop, this all-island cancer research landscape analysis (2019–2024) provides an up-to-date evidence base that:

Maps the Cancer Research Ecosystem

Analysing cancer research publication outputs across Ireland and Northern Ireland, including volumes, trends and citation impact, using Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) as a proxy for the quality of cancer research publications. It also looks at academic institutional contributions and cancer clinical trial publication output, collaboration patterns, funding acknowledgements and authorship dynamics (with a focus on leadership and gender).

Identifies Potential Research Priorities

Mapping cancer site-specific outputs and research domains using the TLO European Groundshot Commission framework (Lawler et al, 2023a), and situating Ireland and Northern Ireland within European and global patterns to highlight areas of established strength, emerging activity and current limited attention.

Assesses Research Activities and Gaps

Highlighting areas of research intensity, as well as unmet needs including under-served domains and missed opportunities for cross-border and international collaboration.

Supports Future Planning

Providing actionable recommendations to be considered by all stakeholders in cancer research on the island, helping to guide funding, identify strategic opportunities, promote collaboration, reduce fragmentation, and ensure that cancer research delivers tangible benefits for patients and communities across the island and beyond.

1.2 Methodology and Data Sources

This landscape analysis uses a structured bibliometric approach to describe cancer research activity on the island of Ireland between 2019 and 2024 (Figure 1). This section provides an accessible overview of the methods used. Full technical details, including search strings, keyword lists, and classification rules, are available in Appendix A.1 (Methodological Notes 1.1–1.9).

1.2.1 Data Sources and Search Strategy

Publications were identified exclusively from the Web of Science (WoS) (Clarivate Web of Science) database, chosen for its consistent indexing and alignment with previous analyses, for the years 2019–2024, using two complementary approaches:

- ▶ Keyword-based search: 57 cancer-related terms (e.g. carcinoma, tumour, leukaemia) applied across titles, abstracts and author keywords.
- ▶ Journal-based inclusion: 277 specialist cancer journals curated from the Cancer Index.

Together, these searches generated an initial dataset of **10,970 publications** with at least one author affiliated with an institution in Ireland and **3,582 publications** with at least one author affiliated with an institution in Northern Ireland. This initial dataset represents the broadest capture of potentially relevant cancer-related outputs before filtering and cleaning.

1.2.2 Data Cleaning and Construction of the Master Dataset

For each record, standard bibliographic metadata were extracted (including DOI, title, abstract, authors, affiliations and funding text). The following cleaning steps were applied:

- ▶ Removal of duplicate records.
- ▶ Exclusion of publications without a DOI.
- ▶ AI-assisted screening to confirm that each publication was substantively cancer-related.

After cleaning, we obtained a master dataset of **7,646 publications** from Ireland and **2,868 publications** from Northern Ireland. Analyses of research domains, cancer sites and authorship patterns in this report are based on this WoS master dataset. Indicators derived from SciVal (for example, Field-Weighted Citation Impact, selected collaboration metrics, policy and patent impact, and some clinical trial-related outputs) use the corresponding SciVal publication counts for Ireland (6,686) and Northern Ireland (2,525). Because of differences in coverage, these counts do not exactly match the WoS master dataset. Where SciVal-derived figures are used, this is indicated in the text or figure notes.

1.2.3 AI-assisted Categorisation with Expert Oversight

To handle the scale and complexity of the dataset, we used artificial intelligence (AI) tools for publication classification, combined with Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) expert review:

- ▶ Tools: GPT-4 was used for semantic classification and Microsoft Copilot for large-scale data handling and organisation.
- ▶ COVID-19 screening: COVID-19–related cancer publications were flagged using targeted pandemic keywords, supported by AI screening and HITL expert review (full details in Appendix A.1).
- ▶ Classification: Each publication was assigned to:
 - Cancer site: 17 anatomical categories (e.g. breast, lung, colorectal, haematological).
 - Research domain: 14 domains (e.g. systemic therapy, clinical trials, diagnosis, radiotherapy, surgery, epidemiology, palliative care).

Classification for both cancer sites and research domains was operationalised using predefined keyword lists, applied to titles, abstracts and author keywords. A single publication was allowed to be assigned to more than one cancer site and/or research domain where the relevant keywords were present, reflecting studies that spanned multiple tumour types or aspects of the cancer pathway (Full keyword lists and categorisation rules are provided in the Methodological Notes in

Appendix A.1).

Anatomical site and domain groupings were adapted from the TLO European Groundshot Commission framework.

A HITL validation process was applied to improve reliability and mitigate AI-related risks:

- ▶ Ambiguous or borderline publications were reviewed by a domain expert to confirm cancer relevance and category assignment.
- ▶ Random samples of classified outputs were checked across sites and domains, with error patterns used to refine prompts and keyword rules.

While this approach substantially improves efficiency and consistency, it does not eliminate misclassification risk. The AI methods, classification prompts and validation checks are documented in detail in the Methodological Notes in Appendix A.1.

1.2.4 Normalisation and International Benchmarking

To enable fair comparison between jurisdictions of different sizes, we normalised publication counts on a per-capita basis. Per-capita values were calculated using the most recent population estimates:

- ▶ Ireland: 5.38 million (CSO, 2024)
- ▶ Northern Ireland: 1.92 million (NISRA, 2023)
- ▶ Island of Ireland: 7.30 million

The same approach was used when benchmarking against other countries, using contemporaneous national population estimates. These per-capita adjustments are applied throughout Section 2 of the report wherever population-normalised comparisons are relevant.

1.2.5 Secondary Indicators and Complementary Data Sources

In addition to WoS, several other data sources were used to provide a richer picture of research quality, collaboration and translation:

- ▶ *SciVal (Scopus-based)*: SciVal was used to analyse Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), international and academic–industry collaboration patterns, institutional mentions, and mentions of cancer research outputs in policy documents and patents. As noted above, SciVal metrics are used for secondary analyses and benchmarking rather than for headline publication counts.
- ▶ *Clinical trials data*: Clinical trials are a cornerstone of translational cancer research, linking discovery to patient benefit. For this report, we examined the cancer clinical trials research landscape using voluntarily submitted publication outputs from Cancer Trials Ireland (CTI) and the Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network (NICTN). These data were used to relate research activity to broader patterns of collaboration and impact. The final SciVal-indexed analysis includes 127 publications from Ireland and 63 from Northern Ireland, with small differences

between submitted and analysed data reflecting indexing variation rather than underlying trial activity.

- ▶ *Authorship and gender analysis*: Authorship patterns and gender representation were examined using the master dataset. First and last authorships were used as proxies for research leadership. Names were deduplicated and gender was inferred using Genderize.io, retaining only high-confidence (>90%) assignments, following approaches used in recent international bibliometric studies. This approach cannot capture non-binary identities and may misclassify some names; these limitations are discussed in the Methodological Notes in Appendix A.1.

Counts reported from WoS, SciVal and clinical trial sources differ because of differences in indexing, coverage and scope. Throughout the report, we indicate which dataset underpins each analysis. Using multiple platforms allows us to combine the strengths of each and produce a more rounded view of cancer research activity across the island of Ireland.

The report also draws on curated **Cancer Research Case Studies** from across the island of Ireland, voluntarily submitted by research institutions, clinical networks, and partners. References to “**Research Case Studies**” denote this collective set, which is presented in a companion booklet published alongside the report and online.

Figure 1. Methodology Underpinning the All-island Cancer Research Landscape Analysis (2019-2024). The initial dataset was the broadest capture of publications by researchers on the island of Ireland. The master dataset is the refined core dataset that was used for most analyses, while SciVal data were used separately for institutional, impact and other analyses. Per-capita adjustments used 2024 population estimates: Ireland 5.38m; NI 1.92m; Island of Ireland 7.30m.

1.3 Stakeholder Engagement

Throughout the development of this report, we have incorporated stakeholder feedback at various stages (Figure 2). Feedback from the AICRI Steering Committee, the National Cancer Research Group and general membership of the Irish Association for Cancer Research was received, helping to review emerging analyses and provide suggestions about the direction of the work. The research group at the Irish Cancer Society also engaged several times to critique the methods, refine the interpretation of findings and ensure accuracy.

In addition, a call was issued for research case studies to the wider cancer research community, which allowed researchers to contribute examples that reflect real activity across the island (see Research Case Studies). This iterative engagement strengthened the report’s evidence base and ensured that the final outputs align with the priorities and experience of those working in cancer research on the island of Ireland.

Figure 2. Stakeholder Engagement Process for the All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Report
 Abbreviations: AICRI, All-Island Cancer Research Institute; AICRIstart (early-career programme/initiative); IACR, Irish Association for Cancer Research; NCCP, National Cancer Control Programme; NCRG, National Cancer Research Group; Irish Cancer Society; CCI4EU, Comprehensive Cancer Infrastructures for Europe.

SECTION 2

CANCER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

This section offers an accessible overview of cancer research activity across Ireland and Northern Ireland from 2019 to 2024. It examines research intensity, visibility and potential influence, and which domain areas and cancer types are receiving the most attention, drawing on previous work such as the European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al., 2023a). We also highlight how the COVID-19 pandemic influenced research, how Ireland and Northern Ireland compare internationally, and where collaboration adds value, whether across borders, with international academic partners or with industry. Importantly, we explore not only academic outputs but also how research relates to clinical trials, health policy and innovation (the latter as measured through citation with patents). The goal is to give all readers, including researchers, policymakers, healthcare professionals, patients, industry and the public, a clear picture of cancer research activity and focus on the island.

2.1 Publication Growth and Trends

Cancer research output expanded steadily from 2019–2024, though with different patterns across jurisdictions.

Ireland drove the majority of growth, while Northern Ireland maintained a high publication rate relative to its smaller population base (Figure 3, Figure 4).

Figure 3. Total Cancer Research Publications per Jurisdiction on the Island of Ireland (2019–2024). Total cancer research publications, 2019–2024, for Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the island of Ireland; Ireland and Northern Ireland totals each include cross-border co-authored papers (not mutually exclusive), while the island total is deduplicated with co-authored papers counted once.

Detailed Findings

Total outputs (2019–2024): Ireland produced 7,646 publications and Northern Ireland 2,868, including 338 co-authored papers. After removing double-counting of co-authored outputs, this corresponds to 10,176 unique publications for the island overall. This is equivalent to 23.7 publications per 100,000 people per year in Ireland, 24.9 per 100,000 per year in Northern Ireland, and 23.2 per 100,000 per year for the island as a whole (Table 1).

Table 1: Cancer Research Publications per Capita on the Island of Ireland (2019-2024)

Jurisdiction	Publications (2019–2024)	Population baseline	Publications per 100,000 people per year
Ireland	7,646	5,380,300	23.7
Northern Ireland	2,868	1,920,400	24.9
Island of Ireland	10,176	7,300,700	23.2

Note: Ireland and NI totals include co-authored outputs; the island of Ireland publication number excludes double counting, and per-100k values are shown as average per year; Population baselines: Ireland — 5,380,300 (CSO, 2024); Northern Ireland — 1,920,400 (NISRA, 2023).

Growth Over Time

Publication output from Ireland grew from 973 in 2019 to 1,458 in 2024 (+49.8%). Outputs from Northern Ireland grew from 462 to 492 over the same period (+6.5%). The total number of unique publications across the island rose from 1,397 in 2019 to 1,888 in 2024. Northern Ireland maintained a slightly higher per-capita output than Ireland across the period analysed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Number of Cancer Research Publications per Year Across the Island of Ireland (2019–2024). Annual counts of cancer research publications from Ireland (dark blue), Northern Ireland (light blue), and cross-border co-authored outputs between Ireland and Northern Ireland (maroon), shown by year from 2019 to 2024. Cross-border co-authored publications are included in both the Ireland and Northern Ireland totals; therefore, the three categories are not mutually exclusive.

For historical context, Lawler et al. (2023b) had before documented how cross-border cancer research expanded after the Belfast/Good Friday Agreement, with joint Ireland–Northern Ireland (IE–NI) papers rising more than 13-fold between 1998 and 2021. The 1999 tripartite Memorandum of Understanding that established the Ireland–Northern Ireland–National Cancer Institute (NCI) Cancer Consortium incentivised cross-border partnership, improving both the quantity and quality of collaborative publications, as well as clinical care infrastructure over time (Lawler et al., 2023b).

The trajectory highlighted in this report provides important context for the 338 cross-border papers captured in this 2019–2024 analysis. Building on this foundation, the North–South Research Programme (NSRP) is enabling collaborative cancer research across the island. Administered by the Higher Education Authority (HEA) and supported through the Government’s Shared Island Fund, the NSRP fosters structured partnerships between institutions in Ireland and Northern Ireland. NSRP support for the AICRIstart programme builds shared doctoral and post-doctoral training capacity in precision cancer medicine across ten institutions on the island. Additional large-scale cancer research programmes supported through the NSRP include the e-Health Hub for Cancer, focused on digital health, and the All-Ireland Cancer Liquid Biopsies (CLuB) consortium (see Research Case Studies).

Together, these initiatives show how coordinated investment and shared goals are strengthening cancer research and delivering meaningful outcomes across the island.

At a European level, the European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al., 2023a) found that while Europe's absolute output of cancer research grew between 2010 and 2021, its share of global publications fell as growth in other regions accelerated (notably China and the United States). In this context, the body of work between 2019 and 2024 from the island of Ireland represents a meaningful contribution to maintaining Europe's research competitiveness. Ireland's near 50% growth and Northern Ireland's high per-capita productivity underline how the island of Ireland is outperforming broader continental trends, reinforcing the value of sustained investment and collaboration.

2.1a Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Impact on Research Outputs

COVID-19 presented a major challenge to cancer research globally and across the island of Ireland. Laboratory closures, clinical trial delays and the redeployment of specialist staff disrupted activity across the research continuum. Early restrictions caused a temporary slowdown in laboratory and clinical research activity. At the same time, the period helped catalyse innovation, collaboration and data-driven studies examining the intersection of COVID-19 and cancer. To quantify this impact, we analysed all cancer-related COVID-19 publications from 2020–2024.

Detailed Findings

Between 2020 and 2024, 357 unique COVID-19–related cancer publications were identified, including 14 cross-border collaborations. Of these, 316 were indexed in SciVal, with an average FWCI of 5.4, suggesting higher-than-average citation impact within the indexed subset. Research activity peaked in 2021/2022, when COVID-19 and cancer publications accounted for 4.7% of Ireland’s and 7.1% of Northern Ireland’s total cancer research outputs. By 2023–2024, outputs had surpassed pre-pandemic levels, despite major service disruptions such as paused

Table 2: COVID-19–related Cancer Research Publications and Share of Total Output (2020–2024)

Jurisdiction/ Group	COVID-19 Publications	All Cancer Publications	% of Output
Ireland (IE)	251	6,673	3.8%
Northern Ireland (NI)	120	2,406	5.0%
Co-authored (IE–NI)	14	300	4.7%
Island of Ireland	357	8,779	4.1%

Note: Percentages are calculated against each jurisdiction’s total cancer research publications (2020–2024). Per-capita values are calculated as (COVID-19-related cancer research publications ÷ population ÷ 5 years) × 100,000. Population baselines: Ireland — 5,380,300 (CSO, 2024); Northern Ireland — 1,920,400 (NISRA, 2023).

screening programmes in Ireland (O’Reilly et al., 2023) and Northern Ireland (Department of Health, 2020) (Table 2).

Ireland produced 251 COVID-related cancer publications, while Northern Ireland published 120, giving an island-wide total equal to 4.1% of all cancer research published between 2020 and 2024. Northern Ireland showed proportionally higher research intensity, with COVID-19 and cancer accounting for 5% of its cancer research outputs and 1.2 publications

Figure 5. Percentage of Cancer Publications Related to COVID-19. Annual share of COVID-19-related cancer publications in Ireland, Northern Ireland, cross-border co-authored outputs and the island total, expressed as a percentage of each group’s total cancer publications in that year (2020–2024).

per 100,000 people, compared with Ireland’s 3.8% and 0.9 per 100,000. Cross-border collaboration remained resilient, with six joint papers published in 2023 (Table 2 & Figure 5). These trends mirror global patterns. A bibliometric study of 4,941 Web of Science articles (2019–2023) showed a surge of

COVID-19 and cancer research in 2020–2021 with a global peak in 2022, focused largely on risk factors, outcomes and therapy (Chen et al., 2025). Rather than causing a sustained decline in cancer research activity, the pandemic shifted attention away from laboratory-based work towards research on how cancer care was delivered under COVID-19.

Globally, around 57% of COVID-19 and cancer papers were reviews, opinion pieces or modelling studies about delays to diagnosis and treatment, rather than original experimental or site-specific research (Van Hemelrijck et al., 2021). Most publications were pan-cancer, reflecting an early focus on systemic disruptions such as screening, treatment delays and patient management. Similarly, Zyoud et al. (2022) reported 7,015 COVID-19 and cancer papers in Scopus by mid-2022, led by the United States, Italy and the United Kingdom. In this context, Ireland and Northern Ireland’s 357 papers (2020–2024) represent a modest but meaningful contribution to the global evidence base on COVID-19 and cancer.

Taken together, the European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al., 2023a) placed these findings in a European context, describing the pandemic as both a setback and a catalyst for long-term innovation in cancer research systems.

2.2 Research Quality and Impact

This section examines the quality and impact of cancer research on the island of Ireland between 2019 and 2024. It focuses on citation performance, publication types, collaboration patterns and how Ireland and Northern Ireland compare internationally in these respects.

Understanding Citations and FWCI

Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) indicates how a research publication is performing in terms of citations relative to similar work internationally.

A value of 1.0 represents the global average for that field and year, while values above 1.0 indicate higher-than-average influence.

For example, a paper with an FWCI of 1.8 is being cited nearly twice as often as comparable studies published in the same field and time period.

Figure 6. Number of Cancer Research Publications Indexed in SciVal (2019–2024, SciVal). Bars show the total number of cancer-related publications indexed in SciVal for each jurisdiction (Ireland, Northern Ireland, and co-authored Ireland–Northern Ireland publications) for the period 2019–2024.

Note: Publication numbers are from SciVal and differ from Section 2.1 totals (10,176 unique publications) due to platform indexing and dataset coverage

2.2.1 Cancer Research Excellence and Cross-Border Collaboration in Ireland

Between 2019 and 2024, Ireland produced 6,682 cancer-related publications and Northern Ireland contributed 2,525 in SciVal. Within this total, 302 papers were co-authored by cancer researchers from both jurisdictions (Figure 6). These SciVal publication counts are lower than the WoS-based totals used elsewhere in this report, reflecting differences in database coverage.

FWCI is used as a proxy for the citation impact and quality of cancer research publications, with a global benchmark of **1.0**. Ireland’s cancer research has an average FWCI of **2.1**, while Northern Ireland’s stands at **1.9**. Publications co-authored across both jurisdictions achieve an average FWCI of **2.3**, well above the global benchmark (Figure 7). In practical terms, this means that cancer research papers from Ireland and Northern Ireland are cited around twice as often as comparable papers worldwide, with cross-border collaborations performing even better and showing substantial international visibility and influence.

Dataset Note

This section’s analysis used SciVal (Scopus) data, which recorded 6,682 publications for Ireland and 2,525 for Northern Ireland (2019–2024). These differ from the master dataset total (10,176 unique publications) described in Section 2.1 due to indexing and coverage differences. FWCI values are derived from SciVal, and ASJC subject areas are used solely for international benchmarking.

Figure 7. FWCI for Cancer Research Publications (2019–2024, SciVal). Bars show the average FWCI of cancer research publications for Ireland, Northern Ireland, co-authored Ireland–Northern Ireland publications, and the world benchmark (2019–2024).

Note: FWCI values are based on cancer publications indexed in SciVal (Ireland n = 6,682; Northern Ireland n = 2,525; co-authored IE–NI n = 302), with 1.0 representing the world average field-weighted citation impact.

2.2.2 Publication Types

Across both jurisdictions, based on SciVal data (2019–2024), nine out of ten cancer publications were research articles (~70%) or reviews (~20%). Letters and conference papers contributed ~2–3% each, while all other formats together made up less than 5% (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Proportion of Publication Types in Ireland and Northern Ireland (2019–2024). Percentages show the distribution of publication types (article, review paper, letter, conference paper, and other) among cancer research publications indexed in SciVal for Ireland and Northern Ireland (2019–2024).

Note: Based on SciVal data on cancer publications indexed in SciVal (Ireland $n = 6,682$; Northern Ireland $n = 2,525$)

This publication-type distribution mirrors the structure of a mature biomedical research ecosystem. Research articles dominate, reflecting strong emphasis on primary empirical work in laboratory, clinical and population sciences, while reviews account for roughly one in five publications, indicating active synthesis of emerging evidence and the presence of experienced groups contributing expert overviews.

The low share of conference papers and book chapters aligns with disciplinary norms in biomedical research, where journal-based dissemination is standard. Smaller formats such as letters, notes and editorials, though limited in number, signal an engaged scientific community participating in commentary and rapid communication. Data papers and short surveys are also infrequent, which is typical in this field given their specialised use cases. Overall, Ireland and Northern Ireland exhibit very similar publication profiles, suggesting comparable research practices and academic expectations across the island.

2.2.3 Collaboration Patterns

This subsection describes collaboration patterns in cancer research across Ireland and Northern Ireland between 2019 and 2024, and how different forms of collaboration relate to citation impact (FWCI) in SciVal.

Ireland: Around 65% of cancer publications involved at least one international collaborator, and these papers achieved an FWCI of 2.7, almost three times the world average (1.0). In contrast, outputs from national-only teams (around 17% of publications; FWCI 0.9), single-institution collaborations (around 16%; FWCI 1.1) and single-author papers (around 1%; FWCI 0.7) were at or below the global benchmark. This pattern underlines the particular strength of internationally networked research (Figure 9).

Northern Ireland: Approximately 67% of publications involved international collaboration (FWCI 2.3), above the world average. Publications based on national-only collaborations accounted for about 25% of outputs and achieved an FWCI of 1.4, exceeding the global benchmark and which may reflect strong performance in selected UK-wide collaborative work. Institutional-only publications (around 7%; FWCI 1.0) and single-author papers (less than 1%; FWCI 1.1) were close to the world average (Figure 9). *Note: In the SciVal classification, “national” for Northern Ireland includes UK-wide collaborations, not just within Northern Ireland activity.*

Cross-border (Ireland–Northern Ireland):

We identified 338 publications jointly authored by researchers from Ireland and Northern Ireland, of which 302 were indexed in SciVal. These papers achieved an FWCI of 2.3, comparable to other international collaborations and clearly above the global benchmark. This suggests that all-island collaborations are consistently associated with high-impact cancer research.

Figure 9. Collaboration Patterns and Citation Impact of Cancer Research Publications from Ireland and Northern Ireland (2019–2024). A) Share of publications by collaboration type (2019–2024). B) Average FWCI by collaboration type (2019–2024).

2.2.4 International Benchmarking

This section benchmarks Ireland and Northern Ireland's performance in *Oncology* and *Cancer Research* (2019–2024) fields using SciVal/Scopus data. The analysis focuses on **research impact**, measured through FWCI, and **research intensity**, expressed as publications per 100,000 population per year.

Dataset Note

“*Oncology*” and “*Cancer Research*” are ASJC subject areas in SciVal/Scopus and cover only a subset of cancer-related publications. These figures are contextual indicators, not a full measure of national cancer research performance. SciVal data are dynamic, so values may change slightly as the database is updated. As this is a subset analysis, average FWCI should be interpreted with caution, especially when comparing with very large research systems.

A) Oncology: Ireland and Northern Ireland in a Global Context

Ireland's research in the *Oncology* field demonstrates both high impact and strong activity. With an FWCI of 1.9, Ireland performs on par with the United Kingdom and ahead of larger European economies such as Germany and Italy (both 1.6). Northern Ireland's FWCI of 1.8 is similarly strong, comparable to Australia (1.8) and above the European Union (EU) average (1.3) (Figure 10A).

On a per-capita basis, Ireland produces around 6.5 *Oncology* publications per 100,000 people per year, and Northern Ireland around 6.4, both clearly above the EU average (about 3.9) and the world baseline (about 0.9). Denmark (about 14.1 per 100,000; FWCI 1.8) and Italy (about 7.9; FWCI 1.6) record higher research intensity per capita, while Australia and Slovenia (around 7.4 and 6.8 per 100,000; FWCI 1.8 and 2.0 respectively) also perform strongly. France (FWCI 2.2) and Spain (2.1) achieve some of the highest citation impacts among larger EU countries, though with moderate per-capita output (Figure 10B).

Taken together, Ireland and Northern Ireland combine above-average citation impact with solid per-capita productivity in *Oncology*, positioning the island of Ireland among Europe's more efficient and high-performing research settings in this field.

B) Cancer Research: Scale and Impact

Ireland's output in the *Cancer Research* field shows a similar pattern of quality and consistency. With an FWCI of 1.7, Ireland performs above the EU (1.2) and world (1.0) averages, comparable to the United Kingdom (1.7) and slightly ahead of Germany (1.5) and the United States (1.4). Northern Ireland's FWCI of 1.5 aligns closely with Germany's, indicating that its cancer research performs well within international benchmarks (Figure 10C).

In per-capita terms, both Ireland and Northern Ireland produce around 3.9 cancer research publications per 100,000 people per year, comfortably above the EU average (about 2.6) and the world baseline (about 0.6). Canada and Australia (both FWCI 1.8) remain leaders in citation impact, while Denmark (about 8.1 per 100,000) continues to lead in research intensity. Italy, Spain and Slovenia also show good productivity and impact, providing a useful backdrop for interpreting Ireland and Northern Ireland's balanced and competitive performance (Figure 10D).

C) Comparing with Larger Economies

China and the United States dominate global publication volume in *Oncology* and *Cancer Research*, but their citation impact is more moderate. The United States achieves an FWCI of 1.5 in *Oncology* and 1.4 in *Cancer Research*, while China is closer to or slightly above the world average (FWCI 1.0) with lower per-capita activity (1.3 and 1.1 *Oncology* and *Cancer Research papers* per 100,000 people per year, respectively). India contributes a substantial total number of publications but has comparatively low citation impact (FWCI 0.7 in *Oncology*, 1.0 in *Cancer Research*) and limited per-capita intensity (about 0.2 and 0.1 papers per 100,000 people per year, respectively).

By contrast, Ireland (FWCI 1.9 in *Oncology*, 1.7 in *Cancer Research*) and Northern Ireland (FWCI 1.8 in *Oncology*,

1.5 in *Cancer Research*) achieve above-average impact while maintaining per-capita publication rates above the EU and world averages. These values represent only the *Oncology* and *Cancer Research* subject areas rather than all cancer-related outputs, but they help illustrate that influence in cancer research is not determined by scale alone. Smaller, collaborative systems, such as those on the island of Ireland, can achieve notable visibility and recognition within the global cancer research landscape (Figure 10).

Figure 10. International Comparison of Research Output and Citation Impact in ‘Oncology’ and ‘Cancer Research’ (2019–2024). A) Average FWCI in the ‘Oncology’ topic area. (B) Publications per 100,000 population in ‘Oncology’ (C) Average FWCI in the ‘Cancer Research’ topic area. (D) Publications per 100,000 population in ‘Cancer Research’. Data from SciVal (Elsevier) based on Scopus-indexed publications (2019–2024). Population baselines: World Bank (2024); CSO (Apr 2024, Ireland); NISRA (Mid-2023, Northern Ireland). FWCI normalised to world average = 1. Publication rate formula: (6-year total ÷ population) × 100,000 ÷ 6.

2.3 Research Domains

Cancer research spans the continuum from laboratory discovery through quality-of-life to implementation science. Using the European Groundshot Framework (Lawler et al., 2023a) as a guiding tool, this report maps 2019–2024 activity across 14 domains, grouped here into four clusters for clarity:

Discovery Science (Bench)

- GENE (Basic/Genetics):** Explores molecular and genetic mechanisms underlying cancer
- PATH (Pathology):** Investigates the biological and cellular mechanisms of disease
- PROG (Prognosis):** Investigates factors that influence cancer outcomes, survival, and disease progression
- TARG (Targeted Therapy):** Develops precision treatments that act on specific molecular targets in cancer cells

Public Health & Population Science (Community)

- EPID (Epidemiology):** Examines cancer patterns, causes, and outcomes across populations
- SCRE (Screening):** Develops and evaluates approaches for early cancer detection
- DIAG (Diagnosis):** Enhances methods for detecting and identifying cancer

Clinical Intervention & Care (Bedside)

- CHEM (Systemic):** Focuses on drug-based treatments that act throughout the body
- CLIN (Clinical Trials):** Tests new treatments and interventions in patient populations
- SURG (Surgery):** Advances operative techniques and surgical innovations in cancer care
- RADI (Radiotherapy):** Improves radiation-based treatment methods and technologies
- PAED (Paediatrics):** Advances understanding and care of cancers in children and adolescents

Living With and Beyond Cancer

- QUAL (Quality of Life):** Explores patient wellbeing and recovery during and after treatment
- PALL (Palliative Care):** Improves symptom management and quality of life for patients with advanced disease

Values in this section are presented as research intensity (the percentage share of research domain assignments), indicating where effort is concentrated across cancer research publications from Ireland and Northern Ireland. A single cancer research publication can be assigned to more than one domain, reflecting research that spans multiple areas.

2.3.1 Ireland

When the 14 research domains are grouped into four clusters, Ireland's research intensity is highest in Discovery Science (Bench) (42.4%), followed by Public Health & Population Science (Community) (27.6%) and Clinical Intervention & Care (Bedside) (24.9%). Living With & Beyond Cancer accounts for 5.2% (Figure 11).

Discovery Science (Bench)

Basic/Genetics, Prognosis, Pathology, and Targeted Therapy together account for over 40% of research intensity, driven primarily by *Basic/Genetics* (18.0%) and *Prognosis* (16.2%). This pattern demonstrates Ireland's sustained focus on molecular determinants of cancer. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 28 discovery-focused publications in Ireland.

Clinical Intervention and Care (Bedside)

Systemic Therapy, *Surgery*, *Radiotherapy*, *Clinical Trials*, and *Paediatrics* together represent approximately 25% of research intensity, with *Systemic Therapy* (8.2%) and *Surgery* (7.0%) as the largest components. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 16 clinical intervention and care publications in Ireland (Figure 11). A relevant example is the **POSITIVE Trial** (St. Vincent's-UCD Cancer Centre and Cancer Trials Ireland), which evaluated temporary interruption of endocrine therapy to attempt pregnancy, informing clinical guidance and illustrating intersections with quality-of-life considerations (see Research Case Studies).

Public Health and Population Science (Community)

Epidemiology, *Diagnosis*, and *Screening* together contribute to approximately 28% of research intensity, with *Epidemiology* (12.9%) and *Diagnosis* (11.9%) accounting for most of this activity. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 18 public health and population science publications in Ireland.

Living With and Beyond Cancer

Quality-of-Life and *Palliative Care* together contribute around 5% of overall research intensity, with *Quality-of-Life* (4.0%) and *Palliative Care* (1.2%) reflecting a small but important share of the portfolio. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 3–4 "living with and beyond cancer" publications in Ireland. Although smaller in volume, these domains reflect emerging attention to wellbeing, quality-of-life, and care quality.

Observed Patterns

Research intensity is highest in Discovery Science (Bench) ($\approx 42\%$), followed by Public Health & Population Science (Community) ($\approx 28\%$) and Clinical Intervention & Care (Bedside) ($\approx 25\%$), with Living With & Beyond Cancer around 5%. Opportunities potentially exist to expand research in lower-intensity domains, including *Systemic Therapy*, *Targeted Therapy*, *Radiotherapy*, *Pathology*, *Paediatrics*, and *Palliative Care* to achieve greater balance across the continuum.

Figure 11. Distribution of Cancer Research Intensity by Research Domains in Ireland. A: Percentage distribution of research intensity across 14 domains. B: Per-capita research intensity (average annual outputs per 100k population).

Note: Based on 7,646 publications: 6,989 categorised and 657 uncategorised. Publications may be assigned to multiple domains, so totals can exceed unique publications (rounding may apply). Framework: TLO European Groundshot (Lawler et al. 2023 a) ; Population baseline: 5,380,300 (April 2024; CSO Population & Migration Estimates).

2.3.2 Northern Ireland

Between 2019 and 2024, Northern Ireland's research intensity is concentrated in *Discovery Science (Bench)* (38.5%) and *Public Health & Population Science (Community)* (33.0%). *Clinical Intervention & Care (Bedside)* accounts for 22.4%, while *Living With & Beyond Cancer* contributes 5.9% (Figure 12).

Discovery Science (Bench)

Basic/Genetics, Prognosis, Pathology, and Targeted Therapy account for around 39% of research intensity, driven primarily by *Basic/Genetics* (13.8%) and *Prognosis* (16.0%) and demonstrating engagement in molecular and translational research. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 21 discovery-focused publications in Northern Ireland.

Clinical Intervention and Care (Bedside)

Systemic therapy, Surgery, Radiotherapy, Clinical trials, and Paediatrics together represent approximately one in five ($\approx 22\%$) of research intensity, with *Systemic therapy* (6.6%) and *Radiotherapy* (5.5%) as the largest components. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 12 clinical intervention and care publications in Northern Ireland. These areas reflect clinically focused research linked to healthcare delivery.

Public Health and Population Science (Community)

Epidemiology, Diagnosis, and Screening together represent about one in three ($\approx 33\%$) of research intensity, with *Epidemiology* (15.3%)

and *Diagnosis* (14.0%) accounting for most of this activity. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 18 public health and population science publications in Northern Ireland. This reflects Northern Ireland's focus on health data and cancer registry-informed research and data integration. The '**Putting Seconds First**' study provided the first population-based estimates of metastatic breast cancer incidence and prevalence in Northern Ireland, demonstrating how registry-enabled research informs policy and service planning (see Research Case Studies).

Living With and Beyond Cancer

Quality-of-Life and Palliative Care together represent around 6% of total research intensity, with *Quality-of-Life* (4.3%) and *Palliative Care* (1.6%) indicating a small but growing focus on patient experience and quality of life. Per 100,000 people per year, this corresponds to roughly 3 'living with and beyond cancer' publications in Northern Ireland.

Observed Patterns

Research intensity is highest in Discovery Science and Public Health and Population Science, followed by Clinical Intervention and Care. Living With and Beyond Cancer is limited but has room to grow, with opportunities to build on strong discovery and population-health foundations while expanding patient-centred and treatment-focused areas such as *Surgery, Targeted Therapy, Systemic Therapy, Paediatrics and Palliative Care*.

Figure 12. Distribution of Cancer Research by Research Domains in Northern Ireland (2019-2024).

A: Percentage distribution of research intensity across 14 domains. B: Per-capita research intensity (average annual outputs per 100k population).

Note: Based on 2,868 publications: 2,442 categorised and 426 uncategorised. Publications may be assigned to multiple domains, so totals can exceed unique publications ($\pm 0.1\%$ rounding). Framework: TLO European Groundshot (Lawler et al. 2023 a); Population baseline: 1,920,400 (Mid-2023; NISRA Mid-Year Population Estimates).

2.3.3 Island of Ireland: Complementary Strengths and Shared Potential

Across the island, research intensity is as follows: *Basic/Genetics* (17.1%); *Prognosis* (16.2%), followed by *Epidemiology* (13.5%) and *Diagnosis* (12.4%). The next tier comprises *Systemic therapy* (7.8%) and *Surgery* (6.6%), with further contributions from *Pathology* (5.1%), *Clinical trials* (4.5%) and *Quality-of-Life* (4.0%). *Radiotherapy* (3.5%), *Targeted Therapy* (3.2%) and *Screening* (3.0%) appear less frequently, while *Paediatrics* (2.0%) and *Palliative Care* (1.3%) remain the smallest components.

These island-wide percentages combine research domain assignments from Ireland and Northern Ireland. These are distributional (share-based) estimates because 338 cross-border co-authored cancer publications appear in both jurisdictional datasets, so they do not represent a unique-publications total.

Taken together, Ireland and Northern Ireland show complementary strengths across the research continuum. Ireland contributes higher intensity in *Basic/Genetics, Prognosis, Targeted Therapy, Systemic therapy, Surgery* and *Clinical trials*, reflecting depth in discovery-led and therapy-oriented work. Northern Ireland places relatively greater emphasis on *Epidemiology, Diagnosis, Pathology, Radiotherapy, Quality-of-Life* and *Palliative Care*, consistent with strengths in registry-enabled, diagnostic and clinically integrated/translational research.

The opportunity presents itself to connect these strengths more deliberately. This includes strengthening lower-intensity domains such as *Screening* and *Radiotherapy*, and more systematically embedding *Quality-of-Life, Palliative Care* and *Paediatrics* across clinical and population studies. Delivering these shifts depends on shared platforms, people and partnerships. Cross-border collaboration can support this by pairing Ireland's discovery and therapeutic capacity with Northern Ireland's applied, data-rich infrastructure. One example is *AICRIstart*, a four-year, €4 million all-island training partnership (2022–2026) funded through the North South Research Programme under the Shared Island Initiative, which is building critical mass in precision cancer medicine by connecting institutions, clinical partners and patient involvement across the island (see Research Case Studies).

2.3.4 European Context

The island of Ireland's cancer research profile mirrors wider European patterns identified in the European Groundshot study (Lawler et al., 2023a), but with some clear differences. Across Europe, discovery-led science remained the largest component from 2012-2021, while effort was shifting toward translational, clinical, and patient-centred areas.

Europe's activity is characterised by strong genetics and biomarker/prognostic work, followed by sustained clinical and population-based research, with growing emphasis on prevention and early detection. Ireland and Northern Ireland show a similar balance: robust discovery, significant population-health capacity, and expanding patient-centred research.

In respect of Living With & Beyond Cancer (*Quality-of-Life, Palliative Care*) research, Europe shows gradual growth; the island of Ireland reflects the same trajectory, with modest but rising intensity, as these areas gain prominence.

Overall, the island of Ireland's research intensity and distribution align with broad European norms. Compared with wider European and global patterns (Table 3), the island appears relatively strong in domains such as *Diagnosis, Epidemiology, Clinical trials, Quality-of-Life and Screening*, while activity in *Surgery, Systemic therapy, Pathology, Radiotherapy, Paediatric oncology, Targeted Therapy and Palliative Care* remains proportionally lower than the European and global averages reported in the European Groundshot study. These observations help to distinguish areas where the island broadly follows international trends from those where it may differ from peer countries. Importantly, a lower share of activity in a given domain does not, on its own, imply that it should be prioritised; in some cases, it may reflect limited research capacity or service configuration on the island. Rather, these patterns should be interpreted alongside disease burden, existing infrastructure and strategic goals when considering future investment, using the European Groundshot study as a contextual benchmark rather than a precise target.

Table 3: Comparison of 14 Cancer Research Domain Distributions Between the TLO European Groundshot Commission Report (World & EUR32; 2012–2021) and the AICRI All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Analysis (Ireland & Northern Ireland; 2019–2024)

Research Domain	World % (2012–2021)	EUR32 % (2012–2021)	Ireland % (2019–2024, AICRI)	Northern Ireland % (2019–2024, AICRI)
Genetics	19.0	17.0	18.0	13.8
Prognosis/ biomarkers	14.6	14.1	16.2	16.0
Epidemiology	11.9	11.8	12.9	15.3
Surgery	11.4	11.5	7.0	4.9
Chemotherapy	11.0	10.2	8.2	6.6
Pathology	9.0	9.8	4.7	6.3
Diagnosis	6.1	6.8	11.9	14.0
Radiotherapy	5.7	6.6	2.9	5.5
Targeted therapy	4.4	5.0	3.5	2.4
Paediatrics	4.3	4.5	2.1	1.6
Clinical trials	2.8	3.5	4.7	3.8
Quality-of-life	2.5	3.2	4.0	4.3
Screening	2.0	2.2	2.8	3.8
Palliative care	1.7	2.0	1.2	1.6

Note: World and EUR32 (The EUR32 includes the 27 members of the EU plus Switzerland, Norway, Türkiye, Iceland, and the UK.) data are from Lawler et al.(2023a) covering period 2012-2021, while Ireland and Northern Ireland data are from the AICRI All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Analysis (2019–2024). These figures are intended for broad comparative context only, not strict like-for-like comparisons, because of differences in timeframe, database coverage and classification methods. Each percentage shows the share of that domain within the total cancer research output for that research domain, not absolute numbers of papers.

2.3.5 Trends (2019 → 2024)

Trends are summarised by comparing percentage shares (in research intensity terms) between 2019 and 2024. These shifts show how the balance of research effort changed over time, independent of overall growth in publications. Overall, the changes are relatively modest, indicating gradual rather than structural shifts in portfolio balance.

Ireland

Ireland's profile remained anchored in *Basic/Genetics* and *Prognosis*, but with a clear shift in emphasis. The largest declines in research intensity were in *Basic/Genetics* (20.4% → 15.7%; -4.7 percentage points) and *Systemic Therapy* (9.7% → 6.8%; -2.9 pp). *Prognosis* and *Pathology* both fell modestly in share (-1.3 pp each), alongside a smaller decline in *Diagnosis* (-1.1 pp). The strongest gains were in *Quality-of-Life* (3.2% → 4.2%; +1.0 pp) and *Targeted Therapy* (2.7% → 3.3%; +0.6 pp), with a smaller increase in *Palliative Care* (+0.3 pp). *Clinical Trials* remained stable in share (4.7% → 4.7%).

Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland's shares were more stable overall, with a small set of clear moves. The largest increases were in *Surgery* (3.6% → 5.6%; +2.0 pp), *Systemic Therapy* (6.2% → 7.7%; +1.5 pp), *Screening* (2.7% → 4.0%; +1.3 pp) and *Paediatrics* (1.1% → 2.3%; +1.2 pp, from a low base). *Quality-of-Life* also increased (+0.8 pp).

The main declines were in *Basic/Genetics* (16.7% → 12.9%; -3.8 pp), *Radiotherapy* (6.7% → 5.1%; -1.6 pp), and *Clinical trials* (5.1% → 4.1%; -1.0 pp), alongside a smaller reduction in *Diagnosis* (-0.9 pp). *Epidemiology and Prognosis* remained broadly steady.

Viewed together, both jurisdictions retained strong emphasis on *Basic/Genetics* and *Prognosis*, while showing gradual growth in more patient-facing domains, particularly *Quality-of-Life* and *Palliative Care* in Ireland, and *Screening* and *Surgery* in Northern Ireland.

2.3.6 Looking Ahead: Opportunities to Strengthen the All-Island Ecosystem

Building on these patterns, several practical actions could deepen impact, while staying aligned with European priorities:

Embed Patient Experience in Outcomes:

Mainstream *Quality-of-Life* and *Palliative Care* measures across studies and services, so patient-reported outcomes inform research, guidelines and commissioning.

Enable Cross-Border Platforms and Skills:

Harmonise governance, data standards and research supports, alongside joint training in clinical research, data science and implementation science to build an agile research-informed workforce.

Taken together, these actions would build on complementary strengths by linking discovery science to delivery in clinics and communities, enabling an integrated, patient-centred cancer research system with European and global reach.

Translate Discovery Through Coordinated Pathways:

Better connect *Prognosis* and *Targeted Therapy* programmes with multi-centre *Clinical Trials* and shared biomarker pipelines to shorten time from bench to bedside.

Scale Data-Driven Population and Diagnostic Research:

Strengthen joint work in *Epidemiology*, *Diagnosis* and *Screening* using interoperable registry, imaging and clinical datasets to support real-world evidence studies and inform equitable access.

Reinforce Selected Treatment-Focused Domains Where Intensity is Lower:

Grow *Radiotherapy* and *Paediatric* oncology research capacity, in line with clinical need and existing infrastructure, while continuing to support *Surgery* and system-wide evaluation of therapies.

2.4 Cancer Anatomical Site-Specific Publication Outputs (2019–2024)

2.4.1 Introduction

This section describes research intensity across 17 cancer anatomical sites in Ireland and Northern Ireland (2019–2024), based on site categorisation derived from the European Groundshot Framework (Lawler et al., 2023a). Values are presented as research intensity (site-specific publication shares) and as publications per 100,000 people per year.

To aid interpretation, cancer types are grouped into three tiers:

These tiers are based on research intensity alone and are not derived from cancer incidence. As some cancer research publications span more than one site, a single publication may contribute to multiple site categories.

2.4.2 Ireland

When sites are grouped into tiers, Ireland's research intensity is concentrated in a small number of high-intensity sites, with a broad middle tier (Figure 13).

Tier 1 sites account for around 61% of Ireland's site-level research intensity and include *breast* (16.3%; 3.7 per 100,000 people per year), *colorectal* (9.9%; 2.2), lung (9.5%; 2.1), *haematological* (9.3%; 2.1), *skin or melanoma* (8.4%; 1.9), and *oesophageal* (7.2%; 1.6).

Tier 2 sites account for around 26% of site-level research intensity and include *central nervous system* (6.8%; 1.5), *head and neck or oral* (5.5%; 1.3), *prostate* (5.3%; 1.2), liver (4.5%; 1.0), and *ovarian* (4.0%; 0.9).

Tier 3 sites account for around 13% of site-level research intensity and include *kidney* (3.4%; 0.8), *stomach* (2.6%; 0.6), *cervical* (2.4%; 0.6), *pancreatic* (2.2%; 0.5), *uterine* (1.5%; 0.3), and *bladder* (1.1%; 0.3).

Within this profile, *prostate* cancer sits in Tier 2 rather than Tier 1. Given prostate's burden in Ireland, this is an important indicator when interpreting research intensity alongside incidence.

Ireland's sustained focus on breast cancer is reflected in previous national initiatives such as BREAST-PREDICT, a Collaborative Cancer Research Centre funded by the Irish Cancer Society (see Research Case Studies). NCRI reports that Ireland's largest invasive cancer sites during 2020–2022 include prostate (11.9%), breast (10.5%), lung (7.5%) and colorectal (7.3%). Set against this context, the publication profile places relatively stronger emphasis on *breast* and *haematological* cancers, while *prostate* remains mid-tier (National Cancer Registry Ireland, 2024).

This divergence is most visible for *prostate* (11.9% incidence vs 5.3% research intensity) and provides a practical prompt for future portfolio discussions on whether research effort should be sustained, expanded, or selectively rebalanced toward high-burden sites that sit outside the highest-intensity tier, alongside clinical and policy priorities.

Figure 13. Distribution of Research Intensity by Cancer Site in Ireland. Bars show research intensity (light blue; % distribution across cancer sites) and per-capita intensity (dark blue; average annual publications per 100k, 2019–2024).

Note: Based on 7,646 total publications (master dataset); site assignments = 7,279; categorised unique publications = 5,248; uncategorised (site) = 2,398. Publications may be assigned to multiple sites, so assignments can exceed unique publications; percentages are calculated relative to site assignments. Population baseline: 5,380,300 (April 2024; CSO Population & Migration Estimates). Framework: TLO Groundshot (Lawler et al, 2023a).

2.4.3 Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland shows a similar tiered structure, but with a more distinct emphasis on *prostate* and a somewhat larger mid-tier (Figure 14).

Tier 1 sites account for around 51% of Northern Ireland's site-level research intensity and include *breast* (12.7%; 3.1 per 100,000 people per year), *prostate* (11.1%; 2.7), *colorectal* (9.9%; 2.4), *lung* (9.9%; 2.4), and *ovarian* (7.0%; 1.7).

Tier 2 sites account for around 33% of site-level research intensity and include *haematological* (6.7%; 1.6), *skin or melanoma* (6.5%; 1.6), *oesophageal* (6.3%; 1.5), *head and neck or oral* (5.0%; 1.2), *central nervous system* (4.7%; 1.1), and *uterine* (3.9%; 1.0).

Tier 3 sites account for around 16% of site-level research intensity and include *liver* (3.3%; 0.8), *kidney* (3.2%; 0.8), *cervical* (3.1%; 0.8), *pancreatic* (3.1%; 0.8), *stomach* (2.5%; 0.6), and *bladder* (1.0%; 0.2).

A key Ireland to Northern Ireland difference is prostate cancer, which is high-intensity in Northern Ireland (Tier 1) but moderate-intensity in Ireland (Tier 2).

Northern Ireland also shows a higher share for uterine cancer than Ireland. In incidence terms, NICR reports that Northern Ireland's highest-incidence sites during 2018–2022 include breast (10.7%), prostate (9.9%), lung (9.6%) and colorectal (9.0%). Northern Ireland's publication profile aligns closely with this burden for lung and colorectal, while placing relatively greater emphasis on prostate and ovarian cancers than incidence share alone would suggest.

Figure 14. Distribution of Research Intensity by Cancer Site in Northern Ireland. Bars show research intensity (light blue; % distribution across cancer sites) and per-capita intensity (dark blue; average annual publications per 100k, 2019–2024).

Note: Based on 2,868 total publications (master dataset); site assignments = 2,796; categorised unique publications = 1,967; uncategorised (site) = 901. Multiple site assignment is possible; percentages are calculated relative to site assignments. Population baseline: 1,920,400 (Mid-2023; NISRA Mid-Year Population Estimates). Framework: TLO Groundshot (Lawler et al. 2023a)

2.4.4 All-Island Synthesis: Current Focus and Opportunities

Across the island, research intensity is led by *breast* (15.3%), *colorectal* (9.9%) and *lung* (9.6%), alongside *haematological* cancers (8.6%) and *skin or melanoma* (7.9%). Together, these Tier 1 sites account for just over half of all-island site-level research intensity and align with major sites of cancer burden.

Tier 2 sites form a broad middle band, including *prostate* (6.9%), *oesophageal* (6.9%), *central nervous system* (6.2%), *head and neck or oral* (5.4%), *ovarian* (4.8%), and *liver* (4.2%). These sites attract sustained but not dominant attention and include cancers with complex pathways of care and significant survivorship needs.

Tier 3 sites remain diffuse across the island, including *kidney* (3.3%), *cervical* (2.6%), *stomach* (2.6%), *pancreatic* (2.5%), *uterine* (2.2%), and *bladder* (1.1%). Many of these are associated with later presentation or poorer outcomes, so low-intensity should be interpreted as a potential shared opportunity rather than a lack of clinical importance. Incidence context supports this interpretation: for example, pancreatic and uterine cancers account for a small but meaningful share of diagnosed cancers in both jurisdictions (Ireland: pancreas 1.7%, uterine 1.7%; Northern Ireland: pancreas 2.1%, uterine 1.9%) yet remain Tier 3 in the publication profile.

Our all-island numbers describe the pattern of activity across Ireland and Northern Ireland, not a de-duplicated paper count. Cross-border papers (338 in total) sit in both datasets, so they're included once for Ireland and once for Northern Ireland.

Several all-island initiatives illustrate how collaboration can convert research intensity into patient and policy-relevant outputs. The PRO-ACT initiative is an all-island, patient-led survey examining the sexual and emotional impact of prostate cancer treatment, designed to inform quality of life, communication and care models (see Research Case Studies). Cross-border collaboration is also reflected in the All-Ireland Cancer Network (AllCaN) Oesophageal Programme, which connects scientists, clinicians and patient partners across six institutions to strengthen prevention, early detection and survivorship for oesophageal cancer (see Research Case Studies).

A complementary, cross-border enabler is CLuB (the All-Ireland Cancer Liquid Biopsies Consortium), an Emerging Hub of Excellence supported through the HEA North South Research Programme. CLuB brings together researchers, patients, policymakers and industry to share expertise and resources on liquid biopsies, including linked biobanks and datasets spanning lung, ovarian and breast cancer across Ireland and Northern Ireland (see Research Case Studies).

2.4.5 European Context and Global Context

To contextualise Ireland and Northern Ireland's cancer-site research intensity profiles, the European Groundshot Commission (Lawler et al., 2023a) reports the distribution of global cancer research publications by anatomical site using Web of Science data (2012–2021), including a European aggregate (EUR32: EU-27 plus Switzerland, Norway, Türkiye, Iceland and the UK). These distributions provide interpretive context rather than a like-for-like benchmark, as the time periods and bibliometric methods differ from this analysis (Table 4).

Globally and across Europe, research outputs are dominated by *breast* and *haematological* cancers, with *lung* and *colorectal* also among the largest site categories. The island of Ireland broadly follows this pattern, but with a stronger emphasis on *breast* cancer and higher activity in *lung* and *colorectal* cancer. Several differences are large enough to be material signals of portfolio emphasis, even allowing for methodological and timeframe differences. Consistent with our Tier 1 grouping, *breast*, *colorectal*, *lung* and

haematological cancers, together with *skin/melanoma*, account for just over half of all site-specific publications across the island.

Several site areas stand out relative to Groundshot distributions. *Skin/melanoma* accounts for a larger share of island publications than in wider European or global portfolios, and *oesophageal* cancer is markedly more prominent, consistent with strong oesophageal research and survivorship activity highlighted elsewhere in this report, including cross-border programmes. *Lung* cancer is also more represented in the island portfolio than in the EUR32 distribution.

In contrast, some sites that contribute substantially to global and European portfolios are less represented on the island, notably *stomach* cancer (and, to a lesser extent, *liver* cancer), which sit closer to the Tier 3 range in our analysis. Other major sites, including cancers of the *brain* and *central nervous system*, *head and neck*, *kidney*, *pancreas*, *cervix*, *uterus* and *bladder*, generally fall within mid-range and low tier bands close to European patterns, with variation such as higher prostate cancer emphasis (particularly in Northern Ireland) and central nervous system cancers (particularly in Ireland). Overall, these comparisons support a tiered approach for interpreting where the island's site profile diverges from broader European and global patterns and where shared opportunities may warrant deeper discussion of priorities.

Table 4: Comparison of Anatomical Cancer Site-Specific Research Distributions between the TLO European Groundshot Commission Report (World & EUR32; 2012–2021) and the AICRI All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Analysis (Ireland & Northern Ireland; 2019–2024)

Cancer site	World % (2012–2021)	EUR32 % (2012–2021)	Ireland % (2019–2024, AICRI)	Northern Ireland % (2019–2024, AICRI)
Breast	9.7	9.9	16.3	12.7
Colorectal	6.2	6.7	9.9	9.9
Lung	6.3	4.9	9.5	9.9
Haematological/Blood	8.1	9.7	9.3	6.7
Skin/Melanoma	3.1	4.3	8.4	6.5
Prostate	4.2	5.0	5.3	11.1
Oesophageal	1.6	1.1	7.2	6.3
CNS (Central Nervous system)	5.5	5.6	6.8	4.7
Head & Neck/ Oral	4.8	4.6	5.5	5.0
Ovarian	–	–	4.0	7.0
Liver	6.1	4.2	4.5	3.3
Kidney	2.2	2.2	3.4	3.2
Cervical	1.9	1.5	2.4	3.1
Stomach	4.6	3.3	2.6	2.5
Pancreatic	2.6	2.4	2.2	3.1
Uterine	–	–	1.5	3.9
Bladder	–	–	1.1	1.0

Note: World and EUR32 data are from Lawler et al. (2023a), covering period 2012-2021. The EUR32 includes the 27 EU member states plus Switzerland, Norway, Türkiye, Iceland, and the UK. Ireland and Northern Ireland data are from the AICRI All-Island Cancer Research Landscape Analysis (2019–2024). These figures are intended for broad comparative context only, not strict like-for-like comparisons, because of differences in timeframe, database coverage, and classification methods. Each percentage shows the share of that cancer site within the total cancer research output for that group, not absolute numbers of papers. Cells marked “–” indicate sites where the Groundshot analysis did not provide site-specific data for World/EUR32, rather than a true absence of research.

2.4.6 Trends in Research Intensity

Trends are summarised by comparing percentage shares in 2019 and 2024. These shifts show how the balance of site-focused research intensity changed over time, independent of overall growth.

Ireland: Ireland's site profile remained anchored in *breast*, *colorectal* and *lung* research, with modest declines in share for each between 2019 and 2024 (*breast*: -1.7 percentage points; *lung*: -1.4 pp; *colorectal*: -0.7 pp). The most pronounced reduction was in *prostate* (7.6% → 4.6%; -3.0 pp), alongside a smaller decline in *haematological* (-1.6 pp). The clearest increase in research intensity share was in *central nervous system* (5.6% → 9.2%; +3.6 pp). *Oesophageal* remained a high-intensity site, but its share declined slightly (-0.6 pp). Several mid- and lower-intensity sites increased gradually, including *uterine* (+0.9 pp), *ovarian* (+0.8 pp), *kidney* (+0.8 pp), *head and neck or oral* (+0.7 pp), and *stomach* (+0.7 pp).

Northern Ireland: Northern Ireland shows larger swings in percentage share between 2019 and 2024, reflecting a more changeable site mix across these two time points. The most notable shift was a sharp decline in *prostate* (16.4% → 6.6%; -9.8 pp). Over the same period, research intensity share increased strongly for *colorectal* (6.3% → 10.1%; +3.8 pp). The largest increase was in *central nervous system* (2.2% → 8.7%; +6.5 pp). *Breast* also increased in share (+1.5 pp), as did

haematological (+1.7 pp). Several sites decreased in share, including *oesophageal* (-2.5 pp) and *ovarian* (-1.9 pp), while *head and neck or oral* increased (+1.3 pp).

Viewed together, Ireland's profile shows gradual change across multiple sites, while Northern Ireland's shifts are more concentrated in a small number of sites. These patterns help identify where research focus is stable over time and where emerging areas may warrant closer interpretation alongside burden and service priorities.

2.4.7 Looking Ahead: Opportunities to Strengthen the All-Island Cancer Site Portfolio

Across Ireland and Northern Ireland, site-focused research intensity is concentrated in a small number of high-burden cancers, with a broad mid-tier and a long tail of lower-intensity sites. This concentration is a strength: it reflects depth in core areas such as *breast*, *colorectal* and *lung* cancer, alongside sustained attention to *haematological* cancers.

In European and global context, the island's research intensity is particularly high in *breast* cancer and is broadly aligned for *haematological* cancers. *Lung* and *colorectal* research also appear more prominent than in the EUR32 and global distributions. *Oesophageal* cancer is another clear area of relative intensity, with a higher share than the EUR32 and global reference distributions, consistent with sustained all-island programmes such as AllCaN (see Research Case Studies).

At the same time, the tier structure and the burden context highlight shared opportunities to improve balance while also considering current research capacity, equity and impact.

Building on these patterns, several practical actions could deepen impact, while staying aligned with European priorities:

Connect Research Intensity to Burden-Informed Priorities

Use the tier profile alongside incidence context to identify where research intensity is lower relative to incidence share for high-burden sites (for example, prostate in Ireland). Also highlight where low-intensity sites with poorer outcomes may warrant more programmatic attention (for example, pancreatic and uterine cancers).

Strengthen Early Detection and Prevention Where the Portfolio is Underdeveloped

Build coordinated programmes that link screening and risk stratification research with implementation and real-world evaluation focusing especially on cancers where earlier diagnosis could improve outcomes.

Scale Cross-Border Platforms for High-Impact Site Programmes

Expand shared infrastructure, governance and data standards to support multi-centre studies and trials, using existing all-island initiatives (for example, PRO-ACT, AllCaN, and in particular the All-Island eHealth Hub for Cancer (see Research Case Studies) as key enablers of data-driven research and innovation

Embed Outcomes That Matter to Patients Across Site Programmes

Make quality-of-life, survivorship and supportive-care outcomes routine components of anatomical site-focused research, so findings translate into guidelines, commissioning and service improvement.

Sustain a Diverse Site Portfolio While Protecting Depth in Tier 1 Sites

Maintain critical mass in established high-intensity areas where appropriate, while considering reprioritisation of domains/cancer anatomical sites that are significantly over represented. Also consider targeted funding and collaboration pathways that help Tier 2 and Tier 3 sites move from fragmented activity to more coordinated programmes, while being cognisant of whether sufficient research capacity exists.

Taken together, these steps build on complementary strengths across the island and support a more coherent, patient-centred and policy-relevant cancer research ecosystem.

2.5 International Collaborations

This section summarises how Ireland and Northern Ireland connect with the global cancer research community. Using SciVal (2019–2024), it focuses on research intensity by collaboration type (percentage share of outputs) and the FWCI associated with each mode. For smaller research systems, collaboration is a practical route to scale, specialist expertise and shared infrastructure. FWCI is used here to indicate influence relative to the global average: FWCI above 1.0 means outputs are cited more than expected for similar publications.

2.5.1 Ireland

Ireland's collaboration profile is strongly international. International collaboration accounts for 65.3% of SciVal-indexed outputs and is associated with the highest FWCI (2.7). The remainder is split between national-only collaboration (17.1%; FWCI 0.9) and institutional-only collaboration (16.0%; FWCI 1.1). Single-author outputs are rare (1.4%; FWCI 0.7) (Figure 9).

Ireland collaborated with 176 countries and regions over 2019–2024. Among internationally co-authored outputs, the most frequent partners include the United Kingdom (40.2%) and the United States (36.6%) (Figure 15). In SciVal, Northern Ireland outputs are indexed within UK totals, so Ireland–Northern Ireland co-authored publications contribute to the UK partner figure.

Beyond the UK and US, collaboration spans a broad spread of countries across Europe and beyond: Italy (21.3%), Germany (20.1%), France (18.6%), Spain (17.7%), the Netherlands (16.3%), Australia (14.6%), Canada (13.7%), Belgium (11.5%) and Switzerland (10.9%), with further collaboration spanning Sweden (9.1%), Denmark (8.1%), China (7.3%) and Austria (6.6%).

This mix is consistent with Ireland's participation in European research networks and programmes, alongside long-standing ties with the UK and strong transatlantic links.

Figure 15. Percentage Distribution of Ireland’s Top 15 International Collaborative Cancer Research Publications

Bar chart shows the percentage share of Ireland’s internationally co-authored cancer research publications (2019–2024) with its top partner countries. Note: Based on SciVal data for Ireland (2019–2024; n = 6,676 publications; differs from the broader dataset total of 7,646). Ireland collaborated with 176 countries/regions; percentages are calculated using n = 6,676.

2.5.2 Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland shows a similarly international orientation. International collaboration accounts for 67.4% of SciVal-indexed outputs and is associated with high FWCI (2.3). A further 24.6% of outputs involve national-only collaboration (FWCI 1.4). Institutional-only collaboration accounts for 7.3% (FWCI 1.0), and single-author outputs are very small in share (0.8%; FWCI 1.1) (Figure 9).

Northern Ireland collaborated with 140 countries and regions over 2019–2024. A key interpretive point is that SciVal indexes Northern Ireland outputs within the UK, so collaboration with other UK nations and regions can be represented across both “national” and “international”

views, depending on the underlying indexing and geotagging. In the international partner profile, the UK is excluded to keep attention on non-UK partners and to avoid inflating the breakdown. Among recorded partners, the most frequent are the United States (33.8%), Ireland (20.2%), Australia (19.4%), Germany (17.3%) and Italy (15.8%), followed by Canada (15.0%), France (14.5%), Spain (13.6%) and the Netherlands (12.9%), with additional links to Sweden (9.8%), China (9.4%), Belgium (9.3%), Switzerland (9.2%), India (8.5%) and Denmark (8.2%) (Figure 16). This spread of countries is consistent with Northern Ireland’s strong transatlantic links and broad European connections, alongside substantial within-UK collaboration captured separately in SciVal.

Figure 16. Percentage Distribution of Ireland’s Top 15 International Collaborative Cancer Research Publications

Bar chart shows the percentage share of Northern Ireland’s internationally co-authored cancer research publications (2019–2024) Note: Based on SciVal data for Northern Ireland (2019–2024; n = 2,529 publications; differs from the broader dataset total of 2,868). Northern Ireland collaborated with 140 countries/regions; percentages are calculated using n = 2,525.

Data Coverage and Limitations

SciVal (2019–2024) is based on Scopus indexing and geotagging, so totals can differ from the broader publication dataset. Ireland’s SciVal coverage is 6,676 publications (vs 7,646 in the broader dataset), and Northern Ireland’s SciVal coverage is 2,525 (vs 2,868). For Northern Ireland, UK indexing and geotagging can shift some UK-linked partner activity between “national” and “international” categories. Partner shares by country can exceed 100% because a single publication may include multiple partner countries. FWCI values are rounded to one decimal place.

2.5.3 Island of Ireland: A Connected Research Ecosystem

Taken together, Ireland and Northern Ireland operate as an outward-facing research ecosystem. In both jurisdictions, internationally collaborative outputs account for around two-thirds of publications and are consistently associated with the strongest FWCI.

Ireland's position within EU research and funding infrastructures provides a supportive context for dense European partnerships, while Northern Ireland's position within the UK research system can influence how collaboration is classified in bibliometric platforms (for example, whether co-authorship is counted as national versus international). This supports a clear policy message: sustaining research quality and visibility depends on strategic collaboration that also enables shared platforms for clinical trials, data analysis and translation.

2.5.4 Recognising the Health Dividend of Peace: US–Ireland–Northern Ireland Collaborations

The Good Friday Agreement (1998) helped create the conditions for sustained cross-border and transatlantic cooperation, including the Ireland–Northern Ireland–NCI Cancer Consortium. As noted by Lawler et al., 2023b, joint US–Ireland and US–Northern Ireland cancer publications have grown more than thirteenfold since the 1990s.

This is also visible in the 2019–2024 SciVal profile: the United States is one of the most frequent partners for both jurisdictions, representing 36.6% of Ireland's internationally co-authored outputs and 33.8% of Northern Ireland's internationally co-authored outputs. This long-running partnership continues to position the United States as one of the leading external collaborators for both jurisdictions.

2.5.5 Conclusion: Sustaining and Shaping Global Collaboration

Across 2019–2024, both jurisdictions show a consistent pattern: **international collaboration dominates and is associated with the highest FWCI**, well above the global benchmark (FWCI 1.0). The priority now is not simply more collaboration, but **strategic collaboration** that strengthens cross-border platforms, deepens high-value partnerships and converts research strength into patient and policy impact.

2.6 Academic–Industry Collaborations

Academic–industry collaboration helps translate cancer research into real-world improvements for patients. It brings scientific discovery together with development, manufacturing, and treatment delivery expertise. While these collaborations represent a small share of cancer research outputs in Ireland and Northern Ireland, they are consistently associated with stronger visibility, higher citation performance (FWCI), and clearer pathways to translation.

2.6.1 Ireland

Ireland’s cancer research shows how targeted industry partnerships can amplify research influence. Around **7%** of Irish cancer research publications involved industry partners, and these outputs achieved an **FWCI of 7**, well above the global benchmark. Even at a modest scale, industry engagement is associated with substantial gains in citation performance.

Key partners include AstraZeneca (6.7%), Pfizer (5.7%), F. Hoffmann-La Roche (5.3%), Johnson & Johnson (4.8%), Merck (4.2%), and Novartis (4.0%), reflecting strong links with multinational pharmaceutical leaders. Irish companies such as OncoMark (2.7%) and Aerogen (2.9%) point to a complementary local innovation base that connects into wider networks (Figure 17).

This profile aligns with Ireland’s established biopharma footprint, clinical trial

infrastructure, and presence of global R&D centres. A further example is *Precision Oncology Ireland (POI)*, a consortium that brings together academia, industry, and the charity sector to advance cancer diagnostics and therapies (see Research Case Studies).

Summary: In Ireland, academic–industry collaboration is limited in volume but associated with exceptionally high FWCI. It links global scientific capability with local innovation and supports translation into patient benefit.

Figure 17: Top 10 Industry Collaborators by Percentage Share of Cancer Research Publications in Ireland

Bar chart shows the percentage share of Ireland’s cancer research publications involving academic–industry collaboration, broken down by the top industry partner organisations (2019–2024). Note: Based on 476 academic–industry collaborative publications indexed in SciVal.

2.6.2 Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland shows a similar pattern in scale, with around **7%** of cancer research publications linked to industry partners. These outputs achieved an **FWCI of 2.5**, above non-collaborative outputs (FWCI 1.9), again indicating stronger relative citation performance for industry-engaged research.

Top partners include Almac Group (17.4%), AstraZeneca (7.9%), Randox Laboratories (6.7%), and General Electric (5.1%), alongside Pfizer (3.9%) and Bristol-Myers Squibb (3.4%). The presence of locally based firms such as Almac and Randox highlights how regional strengths can combine with international partnerships (Figure 18). This also aligns with the All-Island Oncology Industry Report’s wider picture of Northern Ireland as a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME)-heavy ecosystem, with evidence of university spin-outs moving from micro and small enterprises towards larger scale (Henderson et al., 2024) (Figure 18).

Summary: In Northern Ireland, academic–industry collaboration is a small share of outputs but is associated with higher FWCI. The partner mix reflects both local capability and outward-facing networks.

Figure 18: Top 10 Industry Collaborators by Percentage Share of Cancer Research Publications in Northern Ireland

Bar chart shows the percentage share of Northern Ireland’s cancer research publications involving academic–industry collaboration, broken down by the top industry partner organisations (2019–2024). Note: Based on 178 academic–industry collaborative publications indexed in SciVal.

Note

This section draws on SciVal/Scopus data (2019–2024) for both jurisdictions. While the figures reflect indexed outputs and may not capture every publication, they provide a representative overview of academic–industry engagement across the island.

2.6.3 Island of Ireland: A Shared Platform for Innovation

Viewed collectively, Ireland and Northern Ireland form a complementary cancer innovation ecosystem. Both show similar levels of academic–industry collaboration and share several global partners. Ireland’s profile reflects deep ties to multinational pharmaceutical R&D, while Northern Ireland’s partner mix highlights strengths in diagnostics, precision medicine, and health technologies.

This creates a credible foundation for an all-island innovation approach that links international partnerships with domestic capacity. The All-Island Oncology Industry Report (2024) benchmarks the wider life and health sciences base for cancer innovation, noting that Ireland’s sector includes 375 companies with an estimated value of over €45B, while Northern Ireland’s life and health sciences sector includes around 250 companies with an estimated value of €1.3B (Henderson et al., 2024). Together, these assets can support investment, strengthen clinical translation, and reinforce the island’s position within European and UK innovation ecosystems.

Summary: Combined expertise and networks position the island to build a more joined-up, innovation-led cancer research pathway. Better coordination could amplify impact and support faster translation into care.

Key Takeaways

- ▶ Academic–industry engagement remains a small share of outputs, but it is associated with disproportionately high FWCI in both jurisdictions.
- ▶ Ireland shows exceptionally high FWCI for industry-linked publications, reflecting strong integration with multinational R&D networks.
- ▶ Northern Ireland combines local enterprise strengths with international partners, with an SME-led base and evidence of university spin-outs scaling beyond micro and small enterprises.
- ▶ Together, both jurisdictions have the ingredients for a high-value, cross-border cancer innovation network that links multinational engagement with local capability.
- ▶ Sustained partnership, shared infrastructure, and translational capacity are practical levers to accelerate delivery of advances that improve patient outcomes.

Policy Insight: Continued investment in shared infrastructure, industry engagement mechanisms, and translational research supports can strengthen the island of Ireland’s position as a European-facing centre for cancer innovation.

2.7 From Evidence to Action: Policy Uptake and Innovation Activity

Cancer research influences more than scientific progress. It can shape health systems, inform strategies and guidelines, and support innovation in diagnostics and treatment. In this section, **policy citations** indicate where cancer research publications are referenced in policy documents, while **patent citations** indicate where publications are referenced in patents. Together, these provide a practical view of how research connects to real-world decision-making and innovation.

This kind of evidence-to-policy pathway is illustrated by Irish Cancer Society-funded, UCD-led research on *Smoking Cessation Support* for cancer patients, which identified gaps in tailored support after diagnosis and shaped national priorities. The research contributed to smoking cessation being named a 2024 priority by the National Cancer Control Programme, with potential relevance for an estimated 3,700–5,000 cancer patients annually across Ireland’s eight cancer centres (see Research Case Studies).

2.7.1 Ireland

10%

Ireland’s cancer research shows substantial policy reach. Between 2019 and 2024, 657 publications (10%) were cited in policy documents, spanning 1,336 policy documents and 237 policy bodies across 49 countries. These figures suggest that Irish evidence is informing policy discussion and decision-making well beyond the jurisdiction.

5%

Ireland also shows strong innovation activity. 309 publications (5%) were cited in patents, generating 735 patent citations linked to 522 unique patent families, each representing a distinct invention, across 17 patent offices. This points to consistent translation pathways from research into applied technologies and commercial development.

2.7.2 Northern Ireland

12%

Northern Ireland shows high policy relevance relative to its SciVal-indexed research output. Between 2019 and 2024, 297 publications (12%) were cited in policy documents, referenced across 628 policy documents from 152 policy bodies in 31 countries. This suggests that Northern Ireland’s cancer research is frequently connected to international policy and guideline environments.

5%

On the innovation side, 119 publications (5%) were cited in patents, generating 252 patent citations linked to 181 unique patent families, each representing a distinct invention, across 13 patent offices. While smaller in scale than Ireland by volume, the patent-citation share is comparable, pointing to steady research-to-innovation pathways.

2.7.3 Island of Ireland: Linking Policy Influence and Innovation

Viewed together, Ireland and Northern Ireland demonstrate a complementary profile. Ireland has a larger absolute volume of patent-linked outputs and wider coverage across patent offices, reflecting a larger overall research base and population. At the same time, both jurisdictions show a very similar patent-linkage rate (around 4.6–4.7%). On a population-adjusted basis, Northern Ireland shows slightly higher rates of policy- and patent-linked outputs. In proportional terms, it also has a higher share of outputs cited by policy (11.8% vs 9.8%). For context, across European Union (EU) SciVal-indexed outputs in the ASJC Oncology and Cancer Research topic areas, policy-citation shares are typically around 7–8% and patent-citation shares around 4–5%, suggesting the island’s policy and patent visibility is broadly in line with EU patterns.

A more coordinated all-island approach that links health policy research, regulatory science, and innovation support could amplify this combined strength. Shared platforms, including cross-border data governance, translational support, and policy–research networks, would help convert research influence into measurable improvements in care and prevention.

Summary: Across the island, cancer research is visible in both policy and patents. Aligning infrastructures and pathways could strengthen and accelerate translation into practice, while supporting a more connected innovation ecosystem.

Key Takeaways

- ▶ **Policy reach:** Around 10–12% of cancer research publications indexed in SciVal are cited in policy documents across Ireland and Northern Ireland.
- ▶ **Innovation activity:** Around 1 in 20 publications is cited in patents in both jurisdictions (4.6–4.7%).
- ▶ **Complementarity:** Ireland has a larger absolute volume of patent-linked outputs and broader patent-office coverage, while Northern Ireland shows higher proportional policy reach.

Opportunity: Stronger all-island coordination across policy, regulation, and innovation supports could improve translation from evidence to implementation.

Note

Data are drawn from SciVal/Scopus (2019–2024). SciVal coverage includes 6,677 publications for Ireland (vs 7,646 in the broader dataset) and 2,527 for Northern Ireland (vs 2,868). Values reflect platform indexing at the time of export and provide a robust profile of policy and patent linkage rather than a complete accounting of all publications.

Conclusion

Taken together, Sections 2.1–2.7 present a comprehensive picture of cancer research across Ireland and Northern Ireland. The island of Ireland demonstrates a robust publication base, with strong international collaboration, selective but high-impact industry partnerships, and meaningful influence on policy and intellectual property. Ireland's breadth and scale complement Northern Ireland's depth and distinctive industrial and policy strengths.

These findings converge on a clear message: an all-island cancer research ecosystem, anchored in collaboration and aligned with European priorities, is uniquely positioned to deliver both scientific excellence and real-world impact. This integrated profile provides a strong foundation for future strategy, funding, and the development of shared infrastructures to accelerate progress against cancer.

SECTION 3

AUTHORSHIP PATTERNS, GENDER BALANCE AND INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Authorship Patterns and Gender Balance

Not all authors on cancer research publications are specialist cancer researchers. Many contribute from interdisciplinary fields such as data science, epidemiology, public health, clinical medicine, and molecular biology. The patterns below therefore describe the wider research workforce that supports cancer research on the island.

3.1.1 Why Authorship and Leadership Metrics Matter

Authorship provides a practical window into how opportunity and leadership are distributed in cancer research. This section summarises authorship activity and gender representation for cancer research publications (2019–2024) in Ireland and Northern Ireland, alongside an island-wide view of cancer research leadership overall.

First Author

First authors often reflect early- or mid-career researchers who led and performed the particular work

Last Author

Last (senior) authors often reflect principal investigators providing overall direction and supervision (with some variation by field and publication type)

3.1.2 Ireland

Ireland-based authors were listed as first author on 3,892 publications and last author on 3,855 publications. After deduplication within each role, this corresponds to 2,798 unique first authors and 1,928 unique last authors, or approximately 9 and 6 unique authors per 100,000 population per year.

Gender patterns show strong representation of females at first-author level and a clear gap at last-author level. Women account for 53.5% of first authors and 36.8% of last authors (Figure 19), reflecting overall female author strength but a lack of females as cancer research Principal Investigators.

What this suggests: Ireland has a broad/gender balanced early- and mid-career authorship base, while female senior authorship remains underrepresented.

Figure 19: Gender Distribution of First Authors and Last Authors of Cancer Research Publications in Northern Ireland (2019-2024). Donut charts show the percentage distribution of female and male first authors and last authors on cancer research publications.

Note: Gender was inferred for first and last authors using Genderize.io (probabilistic assignment). Analysis is based on 7,646 Ireland publications. High-confidence gender inference coverage: 79.3% (first authors) and 80.1% (last authors); female shares are calculated within this covered subset.

3.1.3 Northern Ireland (2019–2024)

Northern Ireland-based authors were listed as first author on 1,081 publications and last author on 1,156 publications. After deduplication within each role, this corresponds to 867 unique first authors and 508 unique last authors, or approximately 7.5 and 4.4 unique authors per 100,000 population per year.

Women account for 55.5% of first authors and 37.6% of last authors (Figure 20). This mirrors Ireland’s pattern: women are well represented among first authors, but remain under-represented among last (senior) authors.

What this suggests: Northern Ireland’s author base is smaller by scale but active relative to population, with a similar senior-level gender gap.

Figure 20: Gender Distribution of First Authors and Last Authors of Cancer Research Publications in Northern Ireland (2019-2024). Donut charts show the percentage distribution of female and male first authors and last authors on cancer research publications.

Note: Gender was inferred for first and last authors using Genderize.io (probabilistic assignment). Analysis is based on 2,868 Northern Ireland publications. High-confidence gender inference coverage: 78.5% (first authors) and 76.0% (last authors); female shares are calculated within this covered subset.

Dataset Note

Unique authors are deduplicated within first- and last-author roles. Per-capita figures are annual averages per 100,000 population. Gender is inferred probabilistically; authors not assigned gender are treated as unknown (not imputed). For transparency, the share of unique authors with high-confidence gender assignment (probability ≥ 0.90) is ~79–80% in Ireland, ~76–79% in Northern Ireland, and ~79% across the island.

3.1.4 Island of Ireland: Scale, Leadership Density, and the Senior Cancer Researcher Pipeline

Across the island, there were 4,973 first-author publications and 5,011 last-author publications (2019–2024). After deduplication within each role, this corresponds to 3,653 unique first authors and 2,429 unique last authors (approximately 8.4 and 5.6 unique authors per 100,000 population per year). Some individuals will appear in both roles over the six-year period.

A useful way to interpret leadership balance is to separate roles from people. In practice, this means looking separately at papers and at people.

Papers (lead vs senior author positions): In Ireland, there were almost as many publications with a last author (3,855) from Ireland as with a first author (3,892). In Northern Ireland, publications with a last author (1,156) from Northern Ireland slightly exceeded those with a first author (1,081). This indicates that senior authorship is present across a similar volume of outputs to first authorship, and that senior supervision and leadership capacity is visible across the publication base rather than being confined to only a small number of outputs.

People (unique authors): The pool of distinct last authors is smaller than the pool of distinct first authors. Ireland had 1,928 unique last authors compared with 2,798 unique first authors (about 7 last authors for every 10 first authors). Northern Ireland had 508 unique last authors compared with 867 unique first authors (about 6 per 10).

Gender Balance: Women account for **53.9%** of first authors and **36.9%** of last authors across the island.

Taken together, this means that while senior authorship appears across many publications, it is held by a smaller set of individuals, implying repeat senior authorship across multiple papers, whereas first authorship is distributed across a wider group. This pattern is typical of many research systems, but it reinforces the importance of widening pathways into senior leadership.

3.1.5 European Context

To contextualise these patterns, Lawler et al. (2023c) report that the European aggregate (EUR31) in 2019 was 51.8% women among first authors and 33.9% among last authors. Selected country benchmarks in 2019 include the UK (47.4% first; 32.8% last), Germany (42.8% first; 24.5% last), the Netherlands (56.8% first; 36.5% last), and Denmark (61.9% first; 38.7% last). Lawler et al. (2023c) also report Ireland (2019: 52.9% first; 42.2% last). These figures provide useful context, but they should be treated as indicative rather than directly comparable because the underlying datasets, years covered, and gender-assignment approaches differ from this analysis.

However, read against these 2019 reference points, Ireland and Northern Ireland sit above the EUR31 benchmark for women's first authorship (Ireland 53.5%; Northern Ireland 55.5% vs EUR31 51.8%) and above the EUR31 benchmark for women's last authorship (Ireland 36.8%; Northern Ireland 37.6% vs EUR31 33.9%). Both jurisdictions also sit above the UK (47.4% first; 32.8% last) and Germany (42.8% first; 24.5% last). Compared with higher-performing countries in 2019, they are closer to the Netherlands (56.8% first; 36.5% last) and Denmark (61.9% first; 38.7% last) on last authorship than on first authorship. The overall pattern is consistent across contexts: representation is stronger at first-author level than last-author level, and a senior-level gap persists.

Key Takeaways

- ▶ Authorship patterns in cancer research reflect a broad interdisciplinary cancer research workforce, not only oncology specialists.
- ▶ Women account for just over half of first authors (~**54%**) across Ireland, Northern Ireland, and the island overall.
- ▶ Relative to European benchmarks (EUR31), Ireland and Northern Ireland show higher women's representation in both first authorship and last authorship. This is encouraging, but it should be interpreted cautiously because datasets and methods differ.
- ▶ A senior-level gender gap remains: women account for ~**37%** of last authors across the island.
- ▶ Leadership density looks different depending on whether you count roles or people. Last-author roles are similar in volume to first-author roles, but the pool of senior last authors is smaller than the pool of first authors.

Opportunity: accelerate progress at senior level by strengthening pathways into leadership (stable careers, transparent promotion, mentoring and sponsorship, and support for carers), and by monitoring last-author representation over time. This is discussed further in *Career Development in Universities* (see Research Case Studies).

3.2 Institutional Analysis

3.2.1 Why Institutional Analysis Matters

Understanding where cancer research is performed helps explain how capacity is distributed across the island and where partnerships cluster.

Cancer research is produced across a broad ecosystem, including universities, hospitals and cancer centres, government agencies, funders and charities, industry partners (including spin-outs and small and medium-sized enterprises), research infrastructures, and patient and public involvement networks. This section focuses on academic institutions because they are the most consistently captured organisational unit in the bibliometric data.

A key caveat is that hospital and health-service affiliations are not consistently captured or standardised in bibliometric indexing, particularly where clinical activity sits outside academic metadata. For that reason, this institutional mapping focuses on academic institutions as the most comparable institutional unit across both jurisdictions. Hospital and health-service organisations are not consistently represented in the indexed affiliation mapping; a supplementary mapping is provided in the dataset note, but health-service organisations are not used for cross-jurisdictional comparison in the narrative.

3.2.2. Ireland: Academic Leadership and Collaboration

Ireland's institutional profile in terms of cancer research publication output, based on SciVal/Scopus institutional affiliation mapping

for the 2019–2024 publication subset, is concentrated in a small set of core academic institutions (Figure 21), with a long tail of smaller contributors:

- ▶ **Core contributors (top six = 89.6%):** Trinity College Dublin (TCD; 23.1%) and University College Dublin (UCD; 22.5%) contribute the largest shares of academic cancer research output in this dataset, followed by the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI; 14.8%), University College Cork (UCC; 12.3%), the University of Galway (11.9%), and the University of Limerick (UL; 5.1%). Collectively, these six institutions account for almost 90% of academic institutional contribution (89.6%).
- ▶ **Wider institutional base (remaining 10.4%):** The remaining output is distributed across Dublin City University (DCU; 3.9%), Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin; 2.0%), and a long tail of smaller contributors including Maynooth University and the technological universities (generally <2% each).

Collectively, the top six institutions (criteria >5% publications) accounted for nearly 90% of this academic grouping. At the same time, the remaining share is distributed across a wide set of institutions, pointing to an opportunity to leverage complementary strengths through a more coordinated, collaborative system rather than relying only on the largest core institutions.

This concentration also aligns with national funding patterns, albeit descriptively rather than causally. The Health Research Board (HRB) report, *Cancer Research Investment in Ireland 2019–2022*, based on voluntarily submitted information from 8 national public funders and cancer research charities (HRB, Irish Cancer Society, Science Foundation Ireland, Irish Research Council, Enterprise Ireland, Breakthrough Cancer Research, OvaCare, and Conor Foley Neuroblastoma Cancer Research Foundation), reports that UCD, TCD, RCSI, and UCC received roughly 70% of national cancer research funding commitments during 2019–2022 (Mizzoni et al., 2024). This aligns with the publication profile in this analysis, where the same institutions contribute a combined 72.7% of Ireland’s institution-linked cancer research output. This alignment should be interpreted as triangulation rather than evidence of causality, but it suggests that scale and sustained investment are concentrated in the same core institutions.

Ireland’s international institutional links include leading European and North American research centres. Top collaborators (by share of institution-linked co-authored outputs in this subset) include the Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale (INSERM; 4.4%), the University of Toronto (3.9%), Harvard University (3.6%), the Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (MSKCC; 3.5%), Queen’s University Belfast (QUB; 3.3%, reflecting visible cross-border institutional collaboration), and KU Leuven (3.3%), alongside partners such as University College London (UCL; 3.1%) and Erasmus University Rotterdam (2.9%).

Overall, Ireland’s cancer research output is concentrated in a small number of large academic centres, but it is also embedded within a wider institutional ecosystem. Strengthening coordination and shared platforms can help translate core strengths into broader capacity, supporting participation across the long tail of academic institutions and reinforcing all-island connectivity.

Figure 21: Ireland’s Academic Institutional Contributions to Cancer Research Publications of Ireland (2019–2024)

Note: Pie chart shows the percentage share of cancer research publications attributed to academic institutions only, based on institutional affiliations in SciVal. Percentages are calculated as a share of all academic institutional mentions across 6,682 publications, and one publication can be counted under multiple institutions.

3.2.3 Northern Ireland: A Focused Academic Core with Strong UK and International linkages

Northern Ireland's institutional profile in terms of cancer research publication output, based on SciVal/Scopus institutional affiliation mapping for the 2019–2024 publication subset (Figure 22), is more concentrated:

- ▶ Queen's University Belfast (QUB; 81.3%) is the dominant academic anchor, alongside Ulster University (UU; 18.7%).

As above, this reflects an academic-anchor view rather than the full clinical footprint. Northern Ireland's strongest institutional links are within the United Kingdom (excluding Northern Ireland), alongside international partners. Key academic collaborators include the University of Oxford (3.2%), University College London (UCL; 3.0%), the University of Manchester (2.6%), and the Institute of Cancer Research (2.3%), alongside other UK universities.

Internationally, top collaborators include the Karolinska Institutet (4.2%), the University of Toronto (4.2%), Harvard University (3.9%), Trinity College Dublin (TCD; 3.5%), the University of Copenhagen (3.5%), and INSERM (3.3%).

Northern Ireland shows a highly concentrated academic core, with strong collaboration through the UK and a visible set of international partners. Cross-border links with Ireland are also prominent in the international partner profile.

Figure 22: Northern Ireland's Academic Institutional Contributions to Cancer Research Publications of Ireland (2019–2024)

Note: Pie chart shows the percentage share of cancer research publications from Northern Ireland attributed to Northern Ireland-based academic institutions, calculated from all academic institutional mentions across 2,525 publications (publications may be counted under multiple institutions).

Dataset Note

Institutional mapping is based on SciVal/Scopus (2019–2024) and reflects academic institutional affiliations and co-affiliation counts (institutional 'mentions'); it is sensitive to affiliation standardisation and platform coverage. Figures are based on 6,682 publications for Ireland and 2,525 for Northern Ireland. Some publications map to hospitals or health-service organisations, but these signals are incomplete and not consistently standardised so they are not interpreted in the narrative. Institutional shares reflect indexed co-affiliation patterns rather than total activity, providing directional insight into structure and connectivity rather than a full accounting of clinical research.

3.2.4 The Island of Ireland: Shared Strengths and Global Collaboration

Taken together, Ireland and Northern Ireland show distinct institutional structures. Ireland's academic output is distributed across several large centres (top six institutions account for nearly 90% of this academic subset), while Northern Ireland's academic output is highly concentrated in a single hub (QUB accounts for 81.3%). In both jurisdictions, institutional scale is clear, and the collaboration signals highlight substantial partnership connectivity.

At an all-island level, this reinforces the value of coordination mechanisms that support cross-institution collaboration. One important example is the North South Research Programme (NSRP), delivered by the Higher Education Authority (HEA) with research funding provided through the Shared Island Initiative, to strengthen research links and joint programmes involving multiple institutions across the island.

Within cancer research on the island, NSRP illustrates how enabling mechanisms can make cross-institution collaboration work in practice. All-island initiatives such as *AICR/start* (training and capacity-building), the *eHealth Hub for Cancer* (data connectivity), *CLuB* (technology-focused liquid biopsy consortium), and multi-stakeholder efforts supported by charities, such as AllCaN Oesophageal Programme funded by Breakthrough Cancer Research, are early signals that coordinated funding and shared infrastructure can connect institutional strengths and support a more patient-centred, outcomes-focused ecosystem.

Key Takeaways

- ▶ **Research Capacity is Concentrated:** In Ireland, the top six universities (TCD, UCD, RCSI, UCC, University of Galway, and University of Limerick) account for about **90%** of this academic subset, with a long tail of smaller contributors. In Northern Ireland, activity is even more centralised, with Queen's University Belfast accounting for **81.3%** of this academic institutional contribution and Ulster University providing the remaining share.
- ▶ **Policy Relevance:** Concentration of expertise can support scale and help deliver excellence, but it also creates dependency on a small number of institutions. This strengthens the case for coordinated all-island programmes that spread capability across the island through shared infrastructure, training pipelines, and co-led programmes.
- ▶ **A Practical Opportunity for Inclusive Growth:** The input of smaller contributors in Ireland provides a practical basis for widening participation, designing calls and platforms so smaller universities and other academic institutions can plug into multi-institution consortia with defined roles, rather than remaining peripheral.

Partnerships are already a strength to build on: Both jurisdictions show collaboration with leading European and North American institutions, and cross-border links are visible.

SECTION 4

CANCER CLINICAL TRIAL-LINKED PUBLICATION ACTIVITY (CTI AND NICTN)

4.1 Why Trial-Linked Research Outputs Matter

Clinical trials are an important pathway from research to delivering patient benefit. They can connect patients to new treatments and closer monitoring, but they also depend on delivery capacity across the system (clinical trial units, data, contracting, and workforce). This subsection uses publications linked to trial networks as a research signal, not as a complete measure of clinical trials activity. We focus on what these outputs suggest about collaboration patterns, research influence (FWCI), early translation visibility (policy and patent citations), and broad topic signals.

4.2 How to Interpret These Data

- ▶ Source and scope: Publications were voluntarily submitted by Cancer Trials Ireland (CTI) and the Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network (NICTN) and matched to what was indexed in SciVal (Scopus) at export.
- ▶ What is captured (indexed in SciVal): CTI n = 127; NICTN n = 63 (2019–2024).
- ▶ Not a census: These sets are incomplete by design, reflecting platform coverage and submission practices rather than total clinical trials activity.
- ▶ What is included: All publication types under ASJC subject classification, with self-citations included.
- ▶ Meaning of FWCI: FWCI is a field-normalised indicator where 1.0 equals the global average for comparable publications.
- ▶ Small-set caution: Citation-based averages (including FWCI) can be influenced by a small number of highly cited multicentre papers; interpreted as signals, not as a performance scorecard.
- ▶ Topic signals (how to read them): SciVal Topics are created through an internal clustering algorithm applied to the indexed publication set. We use them only to orient the reader to areas of concentration and spread (i.e., indicative breadth/depth), not as a comprehensive mapping of trial portfolios.

4.3 Ireland-Cancer Trials Ireland (CTI)

In SciVal, the CTI-linked set includes 127 indexed publications (2019–2024) with an average FWCI of 7.29, indicating high citation impact relative to global field norms for comparable outputs. The strongest feature of this portfolio is external connectivity: 81.9% (104/127) of outputs involve international collaboration, and this internationally co-authored segment also has the highest measured influence (FWCI 8.6). By contrast, outputs classed as national-only collaboration account for 17.3% (22/127) and have lower measured influence (FWCI 1.2).

A second noteworthy signal is the role of industry-linked publications. Around 28.4% (36/127) of outputs are tagged as academic–industry collaborations in SciVal and show higher measured influence (FWCI 10.4) than outputs without an industry partner (FWCI 6.0). Beyond academic visibility, SciVal indicates measurable reach into policy and innovation tracking: 28.3% (36/127) of outputs are cited by policy documents, and 8.7% (11/127) are cited by patents. These are useful indicators of uptake beyond the scholarly literature, but they remain partial, dependent on what policy and patent sources are captured in SciVal and how documents are linked.

For wider service context (outside bibliometrics), CTI’s *The Value of Cancer Trials* report (Nov 2025) benchmarks Ireland’s clinical trial activity against European norms and describes patient and

system value from trials. It also provides conservative, sample-based estimates of potential system value for subsets of trials (for example, indicative treatment-cost offsets and inward-investment estimates), which should be interpreted in line with the report’s stated assumptions.

Finally, SciVal Topics suggest CTI-linked publications are treatment-focused, with recurring themes in breast and gynaecological cancers (alongside prostate and myeloma), and cross-cutting strands in precision therapeutics and radiotherapy (including hypofractionation). A smaller but visible delivery-related strand is also present (e.g., trial participation, fertility preservation, safety/standards, cost/waste), alongside biomarker and imaging-enabled methods themes.

4.4 Northern Ireland - Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network (NICTN)

The SciVal-indexed NICTN-linked set includes 63 publications (2019–2024) with an average FWCI of 7.4. As with CTI, influence is highest in the internationally co-authored segment: 52.4% (33/63) of outputs involve international collaboration (FWCI 12.7). A substantial share is classed as national-only collaboration (47.6% (30/63); FWCI 1.5). In SciVal, Northern Ireland is situated within the United Kingdom, so “national-only” often reflects collaboration across the wider UK system rather than collaboration confined to Northern Ireland alone.

Academic–industry outputs are a smaller subset than in the CTI-linked set (11.1% (7/63)), but again show the highest measured influence (FWCI 19.7 vs 5.9 without industry collaboration). As above, this is best interpreted as an indicator that the industry-linked segment of trial-adjacent research is particularly visible and cited in this indexed slice.

SciVal also indicates policy and innovation visibility: 17.5% (11/63) of outputs are cited by policy documents, and 7.9% (5/63) are cited by patents.

SciVal Topics suggest a clinically anchored, treatment-focused profile, with strong emphasis on real-world outcomes (response, survival, toxicity, function) and on refining how therapies are delivered (notably radiotherapy/chemoradiation), alongside selective precision themes (targeted agents, DNA damage response, biomarkers). Prostate cancer appears well developed, alongside a haematological malignancy strand, and broader tumour-site coverage typical of a trials network (including upper gastrointestinal, breast and lung). Cross-cutting trial-enabling and patient-centred themes (imaging and risk stratification, toxicity management, geriatric assessment, patient-reported outcomes and caregiver support) remain visible; as with all small indexed sets, topic-level FWCI signals can be volatile and should be interpreted cautiously.

iREACH HEALTH

Investments such as iREACH Health (Queen’s University Belfast; Belfast Region City Deal) may strengthen some of the delivery infrastructure behind these signals, particularly where clinical trials activity is designed to integrate more closely with real-world evidence and system data.

4.5 All-Island View: Shared Patterns Across CTI and NICTN

Taken together, these SciVal-indexed sets point to a consistent all-island pattern in trial-linked publication signals: high collaboration, high measured influence, and identifiable routes to translation.

Across both networks, two patterns stand out:

First, international collaboration is both common and high impact in each indexed set (CTI: 81.9%; NICTN: 52.4%), and it is consistently the segment with the highest FWCI.

Second, academic–industry collaboration, while a minority share, shows the highest measured influence (CTI: 28.4%, FWCI 10.4; NICTN: 11.1%, FWCI 19.7). This combination suggests that policies which reduce friction for multicentre partnering (contracts, governance, workforce and data supports) and strengthen trial-ready collaboration pathways may disproportionately benefit visibility and translation.

Policy and patent citation rates are material but not definitive (policy: 28.3% CTI; 17.5% NICTN; patents: ~8% in both). They imply that a subset of trial-linked outputs is visible beyond academia, but they should be treated as partial indicators of impact rather than direct measures of health-system change.

Taken together, these SciVal-indexed sets point to a consistent all-island pattern in trial-linked publication signals: high collaboration, high measured influence, and identifiable routes to translation.

4.6 Global Context: Positioning Ireland and Northern Ireland in the International Landscape

Casolino et al., (2025) reviewed 89,069 interventional cancer clinical trials registered in the WHO ICTRP (1999–2022) and highlighted persistent global imbalances: trial activity is concentrated in high-income countries, and multinational collaboration drops to ~3% of recruiting trials. They also report a portfolio skewed toward drug trials (with comparatively low representation of radiotherapy and other procedures) and note that several high-burden cancers (including liver, stomach, pancreas and cervical cancer) are underrepresented relative to mortality in multiple regions. These authors also cautioned that growth in trial numbers is not synonymous with higher-quality or practice-changing evidence, and describes a predominance of smaller, earlier-phase studies in the global registry data.

When read alongside this global picture, the CTI and NICTN publication sets suggest that international collaboration is already a defining feature of trial-linked research on the island (with high levels of international co-authorship in both indexed sets, as described above). This is not a direct proxy for multicountry trial activity, but it does indicate strong cross-border research connectivity, an asset that may support more joint, scalable clinical trial programmes where feasible.

In that global context, the SciVal topic signals here (from indexed publications, not registries) mainly help to situate where the publication footprint is concentrated (for example, CTI in breast/gynaecological cancers; NICTN with broader spread including prostate and haematological malignancies). Casolino et al., 2025 emphasise that, globally, research effort can be misaligned with burden for some high-mortality cancers and that non-pharmacological modalities are comparatively underrepresented in registries. That framing supports developing an all-island cancer clinical trials strategy to periodically stress-test portfolio balance by burden, modality (drug vs radiotherapy/procedures), and inclusion (for example, older adults), alongside bibliometric signals. Taken together, the implication is less about “more trials” in general, and more about a better-balanced, burden-aligned, and delivery-ready clinical trials portfolio across both jurisdictions.

Key Takeaways and Forward Look (Policy-Relevant)

- ▶ **Maintain and strengthen international connectivity:** International collaboration is both common and high impact across these indexed sets, but it is substantially higher in the Ireland/CTI indexed subset (81.9%) than in the NI/NICTN indexed subset (52.4%); policies that reduce friction (contracts, data access, governance, and workforce capacity) can support visibility and reach.
- ▶ **Focus an All-Island Lens on Delivery Enablers:** The topic signals in both datasets include enabling methods (biomarkers, imaging, radiotherapy technique, patient-reported outcomes) and delivery themes (participation and operational standards), pointing to shared infrastructure needs.
- ▶ **Support the Industry-Linked Translational Pathway:** Even at minority share, the academic–corporate subset is the segment with the highest measured influence in both datasets; notably, NICTN’s academic–industry slice is smaller (11.1%) but shows excellent impact (FWCI 19.7), consistent with a focus on trial-ready partnership pathways (including supports relevant to SMEs).
- ▶ **Track clinical trials performance beyond bibliometrics.** These data are useful for collaboration and influence signals, but they do not replace monitoring of portfolio mix, activation timelines, recruitment, representativeness, and patient access.

Dataset Note

Elsevier SciVal (Scopus), using voluntarily submitted CTI and NICTN publication entities (2019–2024). SciVal Topics referenced in-text are based on Elsevier’s internal topic-clustering approach applied to the indexed set. Indexed sets at export (10 October 2025) include 127 CTI publications and 63 NICTN publications. All ASJC publication types and self-citations were included. Coverage is incomplete and may change as SciVal updates.

SECTION 5

STRENGTHENING THE ALL-ISLAND CANCER RESEARCH ECOSYSTEM: KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis in this report shows a high-performing cancer research ecosystem with clear strengths and gaps across the island of Ireland. The recommendations below translate the evidence into practical actions for funders, policymakers, health services, universities, industry and patient partners, so that excellent research is more consistently converted into earlier diagnosis, better treatment and improved quality-of-life for people with cancer.

Recommendation 1: Create an All-Island Cancer Research Co-Centre

Between 2019 and 2024, researchers in Ireland and Northern Ireland produced 10,176 unique cancer research publications, with citation impact around twice the world average and jointly authored Ireland–Northern Ireland papers performing strongest of all (FWCI 2.3). Yet research remains structurally fragmented across multiple institutions, funders and programmes. A formal **All-Island Cancer Research Co-Centre** would link universities, cancer centres, registries, biobanks, cancer clinical trials networks, patient and public involvement (PPI) networks and other patient organisations, and industry partners into a coherent, shared platform. The Co-Centre would:

- Connect and enhance Ireland's strengths in discovery science (especially genetics and prognosis), systemic therapy, surgery and clinical trials with Northern Ireland's strengths in epidemiology, screening and diagnosis, radiotherapy, quality-of-life and palliative care.
- Provide funders with a single, strategic vehicle for investment, aligned with European initiatives such as Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, The Lancet Oncology European Groundshot Commission, and the EU Cancer Mission.
- Give patients and clinicians more consistent access to research-active services and all-island clinical studies, regardless of where they live.

Recommendation 2: Consider Rebalancing the Cancer Research Portfolio

Discovery Science accounts for just over 40% of cancer research intensity on the island, while Public Health & Population Science, Clinical Intervention & Care and Living With & Beyond Cancer domains are comparatively smaller. Treatment-focused domains such as *Surgery*, *Systemic therapy*, *Pathology*, *Radiotherapy*, *Paediatric oncology*, *Targeted Therapy* and *Palliative Care* remain under-represented within the overall portfolio.

At anatomical cancer site level, research is concentrated in breast, colorectal, lung, haematological, skin or melanoma and oesophageal cancers, while pancreatic, uterine, liver, stomach, kidney, cervical and bladder cancers, often associated with poorer outcomes, receive comparatively less attention. The goal is not to weaken discovery research, but to consider growing under-represented, patient-facing domains and under-served cancer sites, so that research effort more closely reflects disease burden and service need. However, choices will have to be made, with existing research capacity a highly relevant issue. In practical terms, funders and policy-makers should:

- Consider prioritising calls and programmes that explicitly target lower-intensity treatment and care domains and poorer-prognosis cancers, but only where sufficient research capacity exists.
- Embed quality-of-life, survivorship and palliative care elements into site-specific programmes as routine components, not add-ons.
- Use the research domain and anatomical cancer site distributions in this report as a baseline to track progress of high performing domains and progress towards a more balanced portfolio over time.

Recommendation 3: Elevate Cross-Border Cancer Research to at Least 10% of Outputs by 2030

Between 2019 and 2024, there were 338 Ireland–Northern Ireland joint cancer publications, with an average field-weighted citation impact (FWCI) of 2.3, higher than already strong national averages. Across the full six-year period, these cross-border outputs represented only around 5% of all cancer research publications from Ireland, about 12% of those from Northern Ireland, and just 3.3% of all island-wide cancer research outputs.

To realise the full potential of this “health dividend of peace”, cross-border cancer research should account for at least 10% of all-island outputs by 2030. Achieving this will require:

- Joint funding calls and co-funded programmes with cross-border collaboration as a core criterion.
- Shared academic and clinical posts, integrated PhD and post-doctoral training pathways, and flexible mobility schemes.
- Shared registries, biobanks, trials networks and data platforms, so that collaborations are easier to initiate and sustain.

This target is ambitious but realistic given the proven impact of cross-border work and the existing infrastructure created through the NCI Cancer Consortium, the Shared Island Initiative and the North South Research Programme.

Recommendation 4: Expand Cancer Clinical Trials and Real-World Evidence Studies to Enhance Equitable Access to Innovation

Publications linked to Cancer Trials Ireland (CTI) and the Northern Ireland Cancer Trials Network (NICTN) are relatively few in number (127 and 63 publications, respectively, 2019–2024), but highly influential, with average FWCI around seven times the world benchmark (FWCI 7.3–7.4), strong international collaboration (CTI ~82%; NICTN ~52%) and higher rates of citation in policy documents (17–28%) and patents (~8–9%) than the wider portfolio.

Despite this, clinical trial-related research intensity accounts for only around 5% of all cancer publications on the island. Given the relatively lower research intensity in radiotherapy, surgery, palliative care and quality-of-life domains on the island, there is clear scope to expand non-pharmacological cancer clinical trials (e.g. radiotherapy, surgery, digital and artificial intelligence tools, supportive care, palliative care and quality-of-life).

These priorities align with Cancer Trials Ireland’s Value of Cancer Trials report, which highlights the potential of additional investment to expand surgical and radiotherapy trials, non-interventional and patient-led studies, and decentralised ‘hub-and-spoke’ models that improve equity of access to cancer clinical trials nationally.

To make cancer clinical trials and real-world evidence (RWE) a flagship for fair access to innovation, stakeholders should:

- Expand all-island cancer clinical trials and RWE programmes, particularly in under-served treatment modalities and poorer-prognosis cancers.
- Make patient-reported outcomes and quality-of-life endpoints standard, not optional, in trials and RWE studies.
- Reduce operational barriers to multicentre studies (contracts, governance, data access, workforce), building on platforms such as CTI, NICTN and iREACH Health.

Recommendation 5: Create an All-Island Cancer Intelligence and Policy Hub

Around 10–12% of cancer outputs on the island are cited in policy documents. Moreover, over a quarter of research in each jurisdiction falls under public health and population science, yet this evidence is not systematically captured and often not converted into service change.

Following on from and supporting the recommendations presented by the eHealth Hub for Cancer we propose the creation of **An All-Island Cancer Intelligence and Policy Hub**, underpinned by federated, research-ready cancer datasets.. By linking registries, imaging, genomics, cancer clinical trials, metadata and selected patient-reported outcomes under robust, EU-aligned governance, the Hub would:

- Provide opportunities to collect and connect health data and enable digital health intelligence to inform health policy research, health technology assessment (HTA), implementation science, regulatory expertise and real-world evidence.
- Generate data-driven resources to set standards for early diagnosis, timeliness of treatment, equity of access and enhanced survival.
- Enable artificial intelligence-assisted discovery, trial design, prevention and service planning, while protecting privacy and public trust.

Recommendation 6: Scale Academia–Industry Collaboration through Clustering

Industry-linked cancer papers account for only ~7% of cancer research outputs, but have much higher citation impact, highlighting the value of focused co-creation for translation and innovation. The All-Island Oncology Industry Report highlights a substantial industrial base. Taken together, these findings support and reinforce the All-Island Oncology Industry Report's recommendation to establish an **All-Island Oncology Innovation Cluster**.

Such a cluster will help to:

- Create a more systematic approach to co-creation between academia and industry and allow greater critical mass to be leveraged.
- Provide shared translational supports (e.g. regulatory advice, trial design, data access, IP and commercialisation support).
- Offer tailored training and networking opportunities for researchers, clinicians, industry partners and patient representatives.

Recommendation 7: Build a Sustainable and Empowered Cancer Research Workforce

Across the island, there are only about six last authors for every ten first authors, indicating a relatively narrow leadership funnel, even as per-capita research activity is high. Our research indicates that women are well represented in first-author roles (~54% island-wide) but remain clearly under-represented as senior (last) authors (~37%) in cancer research publications. In response to these patterns, we recommend:

- All-island career frameworks with protected research time, cross-border fellowships and leadership programmes are needed to turn a strong entry pipeline into a diverse, sustainable leadership cohort.
- Explicit gender-equity targets in senior authorship, grant leadership and governance are needed alongside these frameworks.
- A routinely updated **All-Island Cancer Research Workforce Census** capturing researchers, technical specialists and research support professionals would provide the visibility needed to strengthen training, mobility and leadership pathways.

Overall Conclusions

Between 2019 and 2024, cancer research on the island of Ireland has become a high-performing, resilient and internationally visible system, but much of its activity remains concentrated in certain research domains and on a subset of anatomical cancer sites. The sector is characterised by small number of institutional centres and a relatively narrow senior leadership cohort. Our findings suggest that treatment-focused, patient-centred, cross-border and industry-linked research have room to grow.

Across two jurisdictions with distinct health and research systems, the cancer research ecosystem is nonetheless deeply connected through shared history and collaborative networks that span the UK, Europe and the United States. This creates a unique opportunity for both jurisdictions to build on their complementary strengths and the opportunities that exist island-wide and to work more deliberately as a single system of cancer research excellence, powered by a highly productive, influential and driven cancer research community whose full potential is not yet realised.

The seven recommendations in this report respond directly to these strengths and gaps. They propose an All-Island Cancer Research Co-Centre, a continued focus on areas of research strength but with an eye to a more balanced and burden-aligned portfolio, a step change in cross-border collaboration, an expanded and more equitable programme of cancer clinical trials and real-world evidence studies, an All-Island Cancer Intelligence and

and Policy Hub, a coordinated Oncology Innovation Cluster, and a sustainable, diverse cancer research workforce. Implemented together, these actions would move the island from a high-performing but complexly structured set-up to a more connected, patient-centred and impact-driven all-island cancer research ecosystem, aligned with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, the EU Cancer Mission and the 70:35 vision for enhanced survival.

Delivering this agenda will require collective commitment from governments, funders, health services, universities, industry, and patient and public involvement networks. The evidence in this comprehensive and timely report provides a shared starting point. The opportunity now is to use that evidence to design investments, partnerships and policies that ensure excellent cancer research translates more rapidly and equitably into better prevention, earlier diagnosis, improved treatment and quality-of-life for people across the island.

Cancer knows no borders, neither should we.

We need to compete, not against each other, but against our common enemy...Cancer.

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